

RitrainPlus

Deliverable for WP5:
Evaluation of the RitrainPlus
Course Programme

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RITRAINPLUS

Evaluation Report

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Abstract:

The following report summarizes the review of the RltrainPLUS training courses offered in 2023 and 2024. It provides comprehensive analysis based on registration data, course evaluations, as well as a post-course survey and interview study, to assess how participants judged the courses, why they selected them, and which issues emerged when comparing the goals of RltrainPLUS with participants' expectations.

Overall, the courses achieved a high level of participant satisfaction, although some organizational issues were noted. This indicates that the program was successful for those who attended. At a strategic level, however, the program did not only attract the core community of managers of research infrastructures and core facilities, but also a substantial number of operators and other associated staff. This raises structural questions for future iterations: should the program broaden its scope or become more selective regarding participants and offer more tailored content? The data analyzed suggests that both approaches have potential to strengthen the research infrastructure landscape.

Keywords:

Evaluation, Survey Research, Group Interviews, Mixed Methods, Research Infrastructure, Sociology of Science

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Executive Summary

The aim of this evaluation is to assess the effectiveness of the RltrainPlus program and its course offerings in addressing the needs of the field and reaching the professionals who require these skills. This is essential to ensure that a high-quality, practical, and relevant training program is available for Research Infrastructure (RI) and Core Facility (CF) professionals. A comprehensive mixed-method approach was used to gain a holistic understanding of the program's implementation and its relevance within the field. This included structural data analysis, program evaluations, participant surveys, and interviews, which together provide the following insights:

Who were the participants?

The program was attended by individuals from diverse backgrounds, with some noticeable patterns.

- A higher proportion of women participated.
- Most participants have a background in natural sciences.
- Primarily, participants were working in RIs and CFs.

However, there were also participants

- From outside of RIs and CFs.
- In non-management positions.

► Since the program is primarily designed for professionals in management or operational leadership roles, a discrepancy between the target group and actual participants has become apparent. This frames the insights into the implementation and outcomes of the program.

Evaluation of the program by the participants?

The feedback on the program and courses was generally rather positive.

Positive aspects highlighted:	Negative aspects highlighted:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High satisfaction with the practical, hands-on approach of the courses. • Content was well-aligned with professional roles and real-world scenarios in RIs and CFs. • Strong appreciation for the quality and expertise of the trainers. • Networking opportunities were considered highly valuable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear structure and informational gaps made orientation difficult. • High workload and assumed prior knowledge created barriers. • Some participants found the courses too demanding or intensive. • Insufficient administrative preparation and communication before the course start. • Need for a more accessible, step-by-step learning approach, especially for foundational topics.

One major theme consistently emerges throughout the evaluation:

- ▶ Content-related difficulties can largely be explained by the mismatch between the target group and the backgrounds of the participants.
- ▶ This mismatch also leads to challenges in applying course content in practice.

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1. Introduction – Evaluating RltrainPlus

Over the last two decades, Europe has witnessed a marked professionalization of research activities (cf. Papon, 2004, p. 40; Moskovko, Astvaldsson & Hallonsten, 2019, p. 250; Prandner 2023, p. 24), leading to the emergence of numerous research infrastructures across all scientific fields. These range from prominent ESFRI landmarks—exemplified by key ERICs (European Research Infrastructure Consortia), such as ESS ERIC (European Social Survey, providing high-quality comparative data on social attitudes and behaviors across Europe), ECRIN ERIC (European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network, facilitating multinational clinical trials to advance medical research), and CESSDA ERIC (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, offering large-scale access to social science data)—to major initiatives like ELIXIR (a distributed infrastructure for life sciences data management ensuring interoperability and secure access to biological information). In addition, more local or smaller-scale infrastructures and core facilities—such as local archives, specialized laboratories or regional research centers—have also been established.

The development and professionalization of these institutions have been coordinated and supported by the European Commission (EC) since 2002 (cf. Moskovko et al., 2019). Only two years ago, the EC announced it would fund the implementation of 27 new infrastructure projects that had applied for grants during the 2021–2022 calls of the EU Horizon Research Infrastructures Work Programme, making €181 million available (cf. EREA, 2023). These substantial investments form the foundation for the operation of a wide range of research infrastructures, which in turn support scientists by collecting (data-generating research infrastructures) and archiving or distributing (repository research infrastructures) high-quality data.

Research infrastructures are of fundamental importance for scientific research and development. However, alongside investments in and the establishment of such infrastructures, there is an emerging need for training and education in the field. This ensures that valuable hardware and software, as well as their associated processes, are operated and used as intended, ultimately

securing long-term benefits from research infrastructures. Consequently, there is a need for the continuous and professional development of training and educational programmes linked to research infrastructures (cf. Prandner & Sinner, 2022; originally derived from Hallonsten, 2020). One of the few programmes addressing this need is RltrainPlus, which offers a range of courses and training opportunities for individuals working in Research Infrastructures (RIs) or Core Facilities (CFs) to acquire or deepen essential skills.

Following two iterations of the RltrainPlus program, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the overall offerings, going beyond the feedback on individual courses. This document therefore summarizes the steps taken to obtain a comprehensive overview of the RltrainPlus offerings, providing insights into whether course goals were met, whether the intended target audience was reached, and which gaps in the current offerings can be identified. Moreover, it presents recommendations for further improvement and tailoring of the program, so that it better aligns with practical realities in the field.

The following report presents the results of a comprehensive evaluation of the program.

It is structured as follows:

Chapter 1 offers a brief contextualization, providing insights into the field, its specific challenges, and key requirements.

Based on this, in chapter 1 the specific goals of the evaluation study are outlined.

Chapter 1 and 4 detail the methodological approach and its application within this evaluation.

The main part consists of four chapters (0, 5, 6 and 6), each analysing different data points and presenting the corresponding analyses and results.

Finally, the report concludes with a synthesis of the findings (chapter 8) and a well-founded assessment of the program's effectiveness and the extent to which its objectives have been achieved.

1.1. RIs and CIs training need – Why educational programs for RI are needed

In an increasingly interconnected research world, research infrastructures are essential for advancing research and academic achievements. They enable rapid exchange and effective collaboration while providing access to data and literature databases that enhance and optimize the research process both within and across disciplines (European Commission, 2020). To achieve this, infrastructures must offer complex structures with smooth operational functions at organizational, expertise-driven, and technical backend levels. A particular focus should be placed on harmonizing regulatory aspects, standardizing data, and investing in efforts that strengthen both intra-disciplinary and interdisciplinary exchange and connectivity (Larrson, 2017). This is particularly pertinent given the continuous advancements in the field. Evolving research infrastructures encompass technoscientific, sociotechnical, and institutional changes. To maintain their relevance and effectiveness, research infrastructures must remain adaptable and responsive to these ongoing developments. (Ribes & Polk 2014).

Recently, a study by the OECD highlighted the importance of well-structured coordination between different infrastructures, as well as the need to establish effective partnerships with academia (OECD, 2023). While the study emphasizes the significance of negotiating and organizing coordination mechanisms to ensure that research infrastructures operate successfully, it also underscores the importance of well-trained professionals who possess not only the relevant academic qualifications but also operational expertise and a comprehensive understanding of the broader research system. This underscores the need for highly specific personnel requirements, dependent on tailored training across multiple aspects of the field.

Accordingly, professionals working in this field must be proficient not only in their discipline-specific background but also in organizational and communication skills, as well as knowledgeable about infrastructure functions, to ensure efficient and seamless system integration.

At the onset of **RitrainPlus**, it was decided to do a two-step procedure. One, a core program was established, to create an environment that fosters key competencies needed for Ris and CFs. This is at the center of this report and the evaluations provided here.

However, in a second step a **mapping study** was conducted. While primarily designed to identify and address the training needs of professionals managing Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Core Facilities (CFs) across Europe, without a specific program or trainings already in mind, the study also assessed attitudes toward educational programs designed to train individuals working in RIs and CFs, which are pivotal in supporting **scientific excellence, innovation, and EU goals** such as open science and data accessibility (Prandner & Sinner, 2022, p. 4).

While this study provided essential insights into the training needs required to enhance the capabilities of RI and CF personnel, it can also be seen as a steppingstone for understanding **RI-related training programs** overall (the findings of this study can be seen in the BOX below).

Those findings resonate with a broader perspective on research infrastructure in the field. Green et al. (2005) show in their analysis of healthcare research infrastructure; the importance of discipline-specific expertise combined with management skills. They also highlight the role of higher-level mentors in guiding researchers and underscore the need for administrative personnel to understand the workings of the infrastructure and contribute to its ongoing enhancement. To ensure this, the authors stress the importance of **communication, exchange, and collaboration** (Green et al., 2005). In a Working Paper Series Kahanec and Zimmermann emphasized the necessity of international collaboration and coordination, transparency, harmonization, increased data accessibility, and the promotion of new technologies in the context of research infrastructures for migration and globalization studies. They also highlighted the need for data service centers (Kahanec & Zimmermann 2008). In analysis and review of archaeological research infrastructure the necessity of state-of-the-art technology, domain experts, and the critical importance of the ability to understand and manage research processes to effectively support advancements in the field were highlighted (Meghini et al. 2017).

All these aspects underscore the importance of well-trained professionals working in research infrastructure—individuals who not only comprehend the overarching challenges and requirements of infrastructure but also possess expertise in their respective fields.

BOX – RITRAIN PLUS WP2.2 Updating competence Profiles:

The mapping, survey and interview study conducted at the outset of the RitrainPlus project employed a mixed-method approach that covered central RI and CF all around Europe.

The first component was a quantitative survey with 330 respondents; capturing data on professional roles, required competencies, and challenges faced in daily operations (Prandner & Sinner, 2022, p. 11). This was complemented by qualitative interviews with 17 leaders from selected institutions, focusing on leadership demands, organizational challenges, and essential skills (Prandner & Sinner, 2022, p. 28). The findings were validated through discussions within the RitrainPlus consortium (Prandner & Sinner, 2022, p. 41).

The study identified three overarching competencies for RI and CF personnel: communication and stakeholder engagement, leadership and staff management, and deep academic and organizational knowledge (Prandner & Sinner, 2022, p. 4). Training modules thus need to be designed to address practical needs, including **project management**, **multi-level communication**, and **understanding the European research landscape** (Prandner & Sinner, 2022, p. 34). The findings emphasized the importance of tailoring training to the diverse structures and missions of RIs and CFs, which span data generation, service provision, and hybrid roles (Prandner & Sinner, 2022, p. 5).

1.2. RIs and CIs – Training Opportunities

The landscape of training opportunities for professionals working in research infrastructure and core facilities is diverse, but still somewhat limited in terms of formal certification. There are a number of offerings available, including general programs accessible to all research infrastructure professionals, as well as institution-specific initiatives designed for employees within organizations. These range from workshops and seminars to more informal networking events which foster knowledge exchange and collaboration among professionals in the field. Training initiatives are sometimes offered in a broad format, while at other times they are specifically tailored to meet the needs of a particular discipline or field. These opportunities often facilitate learning and sharing of best practices, enabling individuals to stay up to date with current trends and developments.

At the level of the European Union the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives - CESSDA (<https://www.cessda.eu/Training>), the European Research Infrastructure Consortium - Eric (e.g. https://www.eric-forum.eu/2021/05/12/eric-forum-training-on-gender-equality-plans-gep/?utm_) as well as the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures - ESFRI (<https://www.esfri.eu/event-type/esfri-events>) offer various training initiatives from workshops to webinars and lectures as well as providing training materials. Furthermore, there are training initiatives in the respective fields like for example ELIXIR offering training for research infrastructure professionals in the field of life sciences, as well as individual institutions training initiatives offered by individual institutions. TRIPLE, a platform dedicated to promoting exchange and open science in the social sciences and humanities, serves as a specific example of supporting these fields through initiatives such as training workshops and curated toolkits (<https://project.gotriple.eu/project-deliverables/>).

However, despite the availability of these learning opportunities, there are relatively few truly structured programs that offer formal qualifications or degrees. One example of a certified

program was *EMMRI*, a certified master's program in management of research infrastructure (<https://emmri.unimib.it/>). But it is worth noting that this training is associated with significant costs. On the other hand, the *RltrainPlus* program stands out due to its unique feature as a certified training program that is offered free of charge. This program not only provides formal certification but also ensures accessibility for professionals working in research infrastructure, making it a particularly valuable resource for those seeking to enhance their skills and credentials in this field.

While there are various avenues for skill development and knowledge sharing, the lack of widely accessible, certified training programs remains a gap in the landscape of professional development for research infrastructure and core facility staff. Programs like *RltrainPlus*, with their free, certified offerings, are essential in filling this gap and providing professionals with the tools they need to advance their careers in this growing sector.

While most of the findings from the previous mapping of the research infrastructure field as part of the *Rltrain* project were oriented towards developing the courses piloted for students and PhD candidates in WP2 of *RltrainPlus* [<https://site.unibo.it/RltrainPlus-young/en>], the need for a foundational body of courses, that provides tailored input to build such essential skills upon is apparent in the field. In the context of WP3 of *RltrainPlus* two editions of seven courses were offered. Those address core skills needed to run and work in RIs and CFs.

These courses include:

Figure 1: Course Program

Source: <https://RltrainPlus.eu/introducing-the-RltrainPlus-management-training-programme/>

The courses offered through the RltrainPlus program aim to effectively support the development of needed competencies. The need for strong organizational and project management skills to handle the complex nature of research infrastructures is addressed in the course '*Managing the Lifecycle of an RI*'. The course '*Ethical, Legal and Social Implications in RIs and CFs*' focuses on equipping professionals with the knowledge needed to navigate ethical, legal, and social challenges, which are critical in the operation of research infrastructures. Similarly, '*Data Management*' addresses the growing importance of efficient data handling and stewardship in research environments. Courses like '*Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry*' and '*Socio-Economic Impact of Ris*' aim to develop competencies in translating research outcomes into real-world impact and fostering collaborations with industry. Additionally, '*Team Building and Development*' and the '*Coaching Development Programme*' are designed to enhance leadership and teamwork skills, which are essential for fostering effective collaboration and building cohesive teams within research infrastructures.

After two rounds of course offerings, the program's implementation and outcomes can now be evaluated in terms of how successfully it has strengthened participants' ability to manage, innovate, and collaborate effectively within this evolving field.

Following these considerations, the program is primarily designed to meet the needs of professionals who are already established in the workforce and offers them a selection of courses to enhance their specific skills in the field, culminating in a certified qualification. Some courses, such as *'Data Management'*, *'Team Building and Development'*, or *'Coaching Development Programme'*, are specifically tailored for individuals in roles with management responsibilities. These courses help enhance their skills, support them in overcoming workplace challenges, and improve overall workflows. Other courses, however, take a broader approach and are open to a wider audience without being tied to a specific role, while still requiring a certain level of prior knowledge.

These courses were not directly based on the exploratory studies from WP2, but they were designed to address needs identified in the field and specifically aim to improve skills and promote professional development.

1.3. Evaluation – A Social Research Method for Practical Appliance

The process of evaluation plays a critical role in understanding and enhancing programs by providing insights into their implementation and effectiveness. In the case of the RltrainPlus program, which focuses on advancing the professional training of individuals in Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Core Facilities (CFs), evaluation serves as a key instrument to assess the perceived outcomes of the courses, and it can be used to understand how original goals are in alignment with practical needs and perceptions in the field. This chapter explores the theoretical underpinnings and applies methodologies of evaluation, setting the stage for an in-depth examination of its role in the RltrainPlus context.

The process of evaluation, seen as a scientific and policy-oriented methodology, has gained popularity over the past few decades as a rational approach to analyzing projects, programs, individuals, and more (Beywl & Widmer, 2009; Hennenfeld et al, 2015). It serves as a tool to

legitimize, assess, and improve these efforts. Especially in the educational sector, evaluation has experienced successful development — with some bumps and periods of slowdowns, particularly since the standardization and transnationalization of the sector, and the increasing implementation of a scientific approach to program development. Moreover, the rising costs of education have heightened the need for resource-efficient programs (Böttcher & Hence, 2016). The significant expansion of the field of evaluation, originating in North America and subsequently spreading to Europe, was accompanied by a process of professionalization and institutionalization, distinguishing the everyday use of the term "evaluation" from its meaning as a scientific, methodological approach (Beywl, Widmer, 2009). This differentiation became particularly necessary due to the widespread adoption of evaluation as a practical tool.

Evaluation can serve various purposes depending on the subject matter, context, and the authorities or actors involved. However, it is closely associated with governance, situated within societal developments and the broader trend toward the rationalization of processes. This emphasis on practical application distinguishes evaluation from other social empirical research. While evaluation prioritizes practical outcomes, such as improving processes or informing decision-making, the generation of knowledge may serve as a secondary goal—but it is not necessarily required. In contrast, other empirical studies primarily focus on the production of knowledge, often without immediate practical application. Mark et al. (2000, p. 63) take the concept of evaluation a step further, framing its overarching purpose as “social betterment.” In their view, evaluation should aim to improve the conditions of its given objectives, ensuring that its findings lead to meaningful enhancements. This perspective underscores the idea that the ultimate goal of any evaluation process should be to foster positive change. The evaluation of the *RitrainPlus* program must, therefore, be understood as a practical initiative within the field of research infrastructure, with the primary goal of advancing the development process and fostering positive growth in the field, rather than being an independent investigation pursued solely for the sake of research.

While the specific reasons for conducting evaluations can vary, numerous authors have categorized these motivations into distinct frameworks. For the purposes of this report, we will focus on Hans-Jürgen Hense's (2006) approach, which identifies four fundamental functions of evaluation. These functions are organized along two dimensions: **action** and **knowledge**. The functions Development, Legitimation, Decision-Making and Learning then can either facilitate the process or add value to the product. This evaluation places a strong emphasis on the **development function**, aiming to enhance the program's design and practical execution. Additionally, the program's legitimacy is assessed through the review of its practical relevance and applicability, serving a **legitimation function** for this evaluation. Moreover, the **learning function** provides valuable insights into the specific needs of RI and CF professionals, establishing a solid foundation for future training initiatives in these areas.

The evaluation of the RltrainPlus project strongly emphasizes the practical orientation outlined above. While the generation of knowledge in the field of Research Infrastructure (RI) and Core Facility (CF) training is both beneficial and relevant, the primary focus of this evaluation is on the implementation of the program and the generation of actionable, practice-oriented outcomes. The empirical research conducted through various methodologies is intended to produce results that directly inform and support the practical implementation of the program. This approach ensures that the evaluation not only contributes to understanding the program's dynamics but also facilitates improvements that enhance its effectiveness in meeting the needs of its target audience. By prioritizing practical application, the RltrainPlus evaluation underscores its commitment to fostering tangible advancements in professional training and capacity-building within the RI and CF sectors.

1.3.1. Implementation Approaches in Evaluation Studies

Several factors influence the quality of a program. On the one hand, the program's context determines what works best, which approaches can be implemented, and how effectively they can be applied. On the other hand, the participants dictate the specific needs and priorities that must be addressed. Consequently, evaluation and its method also can look at specific aspects of a program and the evaluation process can be quite complex. Therefore, evaluation is necessarily an interdisciplinary field where various methodological approaches can be applied. Since evaluation research is primarily based on commissioned studies there are specific requirements that must be addressed during the research process. These requirements may relate to resource constraints but also include managing contradictions between the role of a service provider and the integrity of the academic research process (Baur & Blasius, 2022, p. 197f).

To ensure a valuable, comprehensive evaluation, specific standards should be adhered to. According to the German Evaluation Society (DeGEval), scientific evaluation should adhere to the following four characteristics (DeGEval, 2016).

- Utility

Utility is a central focus for the following study, as the evaluation addresses the needs within the field for an advanced professional development program while also exploring the specific needs of the participants. This ensures that the evaluation remains relevant and useful for improving future training efforts.

- Feasibility

In terms of feasibility, the evaluation utilizes a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a broad and insightful perspective on the area of interest. By leveraging existing data and efficiently utilizing available resources, the evaluation maintains a high degree of efficiency, generating valuable input with minimal effort.

- Propriety

The principle of propriety is also paramount throughout the evaluation process. All stakeholders and participants are treated with respect, ensuring that ethical guidelines are adhered to and that the evaluation process remains fair and transparent.

- Accuracy

Finally, accuracy is emphasized through thorough background research and contextual analysis, ensuring an accurate representation of the field of interests and the program's significance. This involves embedding the program within the broader structures of Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Core Facilities (CFs) while taking into account the underlying dynamics that influence its implementation and outcomes.

By adhering to these fundamental principles—utility, feasibility, propriety, and accuracy—the evaluation aims to provide a comprehensive and well-rounded assessment of the program. This approach ensures that the evaluation not only meets the practical needs of the field but also upholds high scientific standards. Through a careful balance of methodological rigor, ethical responsibility, and contextual sensitivity, evaluation studies seek to deliver meaningful insights that support the continuous development and enhancement of professional training programs within Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities. Ultimately, the goal is to contribute to the sustainable growth and effectiveness of the field by offering valuable, actionable feedback that informs future initiatives.

2. Goals of the RltrainPlus Evaluation

Building on the previously outlined objectives and potential impacts of evaluations as well as a short recap of the development of the *RltrainPlus* program, the primary objective of the evaluation is to gain insights into the backgrounds and motivations of participants and how they assess the quality of the offerings.

To assess the effectiveness and impact of the courses, this will not only include a description of people staying with the program or not but also include their attitudes and perceptions towards RI and the broader scientific landscape in general and what brought them to sign up and participate and if they would be inclined to do so again.

To deal with this the evaluation is structured in three parts:

The first part of the evaluation tries to identify who signed up and who participated in the RltrainPlus courses. With this it becomes possible to identify if the goal of RltrainPlus, to train current and future leaders and managers of research infrastructure and core facilities, could be reached.

This is a formative evaluation to identify if the seven courses offered in RltrainPlus plus are able to reach the designated community or if some of them might miss the mark. This part of the evaluation builds on sign up data and shows the professionals who signed up, as well as those who were selected, which type scientific domain and hierarchical position they came for. Overall this section of the evaluation is concerned with the participants, and their professional or educational backgrounds.

The criteria for success at that point of the evaluation are as follows:

- **Primary criteria for part one of the evaluation [Target group]:**

Were the people signing up in managerial or higher-ranking positions in Research Infrastructure?

This is the primary concern as the program targets managers of RI and not operators per definition.

- **Secondary criteria for part one of the evaluation 1 [Diversity of Disciplines]:**

Are the selected participants covering the full range of scientific disciplines or are they focused on particular topics?

- **Secondary criteria for part one of the evaluation 2:**

Are there specific courses that were failing to attract the core target group? If yes, which ones?

Figure 2: Goals of Evaluation 1

The second part of the evaluation will take the feedback the participants provided to the seven courses into account. The primary criteria for part two of the evaluation will be the identification of courses that had a better match with the expected core target group and the follow-up examination, if those were differently evaluated than others, with a lower match and how so. The secondary criteria for this part of the evaluation include considerations presented by the participants at both the **organizational level** and the **content level**.

Figure 3: Goals of Evaluation 2

For these two steps the evaluation will be use reporting's on the offerings from 2023 and 2024, via a descriptive analysis of structural data as well as course evaluations. Additionally, findings from these steps concerning the connection between course feedback and will be further explored through the analysis of an post-hoc survey.

The third and most comprehensive part of the evaluation will be tied to post-hoc studies, conducted in late 2024 and early 2025.

It focuses on

- what motivates RI professionals to use the program's offerings?

As well as

- how they engage with the program, and for what specific purposes?

The first question aims to identify areas for improvement in the program's processes and workflows, ensuring an effortless experience for participants and optimal functionality of the program, as well as an effective use of resources. The second question provides a foundational understanding of the audience, enabling the program to be tailored to meet the specific needs of its users. Additionally, these insights help us better understand the dynamics within the landscape of Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities. They offer a deeper understanding of the system, its stakeholders, and how they utilize and benefit from the program. This knowledge can further inform strategies to enhance the program's relevance and impact within the broader context of the research infrastructure ecosystem.

Figure 4: Goals of Evaluation 3

3. Multimethod Approach to the RltrainPlus Evaluation

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the implementation and execution of the RltrainPlus program, a mixed-method approach was employed. This approach allows for the analysis of various aspects of the program while enhancing the quality of results through triangulation at multiple levels. Triangulation serves a dual purpose: on the one hand, it broadens perspectives and enriches findings; on the other hand, it strengthens and verifies the results (Baur & Blasius, 2022, p. 165ff).

Initially, structural data concerning the background of participants, their interests, and the scope of their engagement with the program (e.g., the number and types of courses attended) provides a solid foundation and initial insights into the program's utilization. The data was gathered during the application for the program. This analysis helps to better understand who takes advantage of the offered courses and how they interact with the program.

This structural analysis is complemented by initial participant reviews of the courses they attended, offering a direct evaluation of the program's content and delivery.

Furthermore, a survey was distributed to all participants, and the responses provided valuable insights into the interaction between the program and its audience. This allowed for the application of multivariate analysis, providing additional insights into potential relationships within the data.

Lastly, to gain a more profound understanding, qualitative focus group discussions were conducted. These discussions explored the participants' specific experiences, expectations, and perspectives regarding the program, providing nuanced insights that could not be captured through quantitative methods alone.

Figure 5: Multi-Method Evaluation

The mixed-method approach employed in the evaluation of the RltrainPlus program ensures that different methods complement each other, providing context to the results and addressing gaps in data quality or areas where certain methods may have limitations. Structural data, participant reviews, survey responses, and qualitative focus group discussions each contribute distinct perspectives that, when integrated, form a holistic understanding of the program. This comprehensive approach ensures that the results are not viewed in isolation but are woven together to construct an overarching narrative of the program's effectiveness and impact.

By triangulating data from various sources, the evaluation not only enhances the reliability and validity of the findings but also enriches the overall analysis. Structural data lays the groundwork by illustrating participant demographics and engagement patterns, while participant reviews offer immediate feedback on course content and delivery. Survey data further elucidates interactions between the program and its audience, revealing underlying relationships and trends through multivariate analysis. Qualitative focus groups add depth by capturing participants' personal experiences and expectations, providing valuable insights that quantitative data alone cannot convey.

Ultimately, this integrated evaluation approach ensures that the assessment of the *RitrainPlus* program is both thorough and reflective of the broader context of research infrastructures and their structural specificities. The results contribute to a nuanced understanding of the program's strengths and areas for improvement, offering a reliable basis for future development and strategic planning within the field.

4. Introduction to Results

After this section the results of the evaluation of the *RitrainPlus* program are presented, based on the mixed-method approach outlined earlier. The findings are structured into four chapters, each covering different dimensions of the collected data and focusing on different goals. These results will be introduced step by step, with each chapter contributing to a deeper understanding of the program’s effectiveness.

Figure 6: Results and Connections

The analysis is framed within the specific context of the challenges and characteristics inherent to the field of research infrastructure. In addition to addressing the program’s objectives, the findings will be contextualized by drawing connections to the realities in the sector as well as

between the structural data, participant feedback, surveys, and focus group discussions. This setup allows us to explore both the individual components and the overall impact of the program, while highlighting key patterns and relationships across the different data sources. Each chapter presents a -or several- conclusion(s) based on the specific results, along with a reflection on the overall insights gathered. The results will be linked across chapters to provide a cohesive and comprehensive analysis, ultimately leading to a unified, conclusive evaluation of the program's effectiveness, usefulness, and alignment with its objectives.

The first part (see

Structural Data) provides insight into the individuals applying for and enrolling in the RitrainPlus program. It is based on structural data collected through the application process. By analyzing socio-demographic variables, it can be assessed whether the applicants and participants align with the program's initial target group. Additionally, an analysis of the courses chosen by participants provides further insight into how successfully individual courses have attracted the target group.

Building on this, the feedback collected by the program after course completion is briefly analyzed and presented (see

Course Assessments). This feedback is then contextualized concerning the course specifics identified in the previous section.

In chapter 7 (see

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Survey on Participants Perspectives and) the data collected from a participant survey is analyzed. First, the sample is compared to the overall participant population, as presented in Chapter 5

Structural Data, based on relevant characteristics. Furthermore, it is examined to what extent the survey reached the target group in order to contextualize the subsequent findings.

The background, motivations, and aspirations of the participants are then analyzed descriptively to provide insight into their contexts and perspectives. Additionally, general program feedback as well as evaluations of specific courses are presented, with results broken down in relation to the target group. Finally, correlations are examined to gain further insights into the course selection of the target group and the participants assessment of the program.

Lastly, the results of an interview study (see

Deeper Insight - Qualitative Interviews) are examined, providing additional insights into the perspectives and motivations of program participants. After presenting the different aspects of their viewpoints, the responses are further structured through a typology. This typology is then interpreted in the context of the insights gained in the earlier chapters regarding the target group.

5. Structural Data

For the first section, the structural data provided by the program’s administration is analysed to gain insights into the participants' backgrounds and enrolment behaviour. This structural data consists of information gathered during the application process and recorded upon enrolment in the program. It primarily includes participants' academic and professional backgrounds, as well as demographic data such as age, gender, nationality, and country of employment.

Any additional data that could be used to identify participants will not be included in the analysis for this evaluation.

5.1. Methodology

For the analysis, the datasets were initially cleaned and systematized to enable the integration of different data points. After consolidating all data and cases, a dataset comprising 235 individuals was generated. These individuals either participated in one or more courses or applied for one or multiple courses.

The data was descriptively analyzed using SPSS, with a primary focus on the composition of the group of interested participants.

Figure 7: Process Application Data

Finally, cross-tabulations are presented to identify potential relationships between course content and socio-demographic characteristics, as well as between the courses themselves.

5.2. User Demographic – Who expressed interest?

Over the two years the program has been active, 235 individuals expressed interest and applied for at least one of the offered courses. Of these, 199 - representing nearly 85 percent - went on to enrol in one or more of the courses. This shows that the initial interest in the program was successfully transferred into active participation, with more than four out of five applicants. There is no information available regarding why some individuals did not move on to participate in the program, whether this can be attributed to personal or organizational factors. Generally speaking, it should be noted that in terms of age, gender, education, or field of work, the composition of participants is quite like that of the applicants. There are no indications to suggest that a specific type of individual, based on these factors, was more likely to proceed to participate in the program's courses.

Figure 8: Enrolment rate

5.2.2 Demographics

A large proportion of the individuals applying for and participating in the *RltrainPlus* program are women, comprising approximately two-thirds of the groups (see Table 1). The discussion on gender differences in training opportunities for working individuals lacks consensus, with some arguing that women face limitations due to family responsibilities and structural barriers, others claiming no significant gender-based differences, and yet others pointing to a higher likelihood of women participating in training programs (Dieckhoff & Steiber 2011). Furthermore, we cannot make any statements about the gender distribution in the field of research infrastructure, which would allow for identifying any deviations regarding participation in the RltrainPlus program. However, it is evident that this program attracts women more strongly than men.

Regarding the age of individuals, approximately three-quarters are between 35 and 54 years old. One person under the age of 25 applied but did not proceed to participate in any courses. Around 15 percent of applicants were aged 25 to 34, while about 10 percent were older than 54. This makes up for an average age of around 43 years (with a standard deviation of 8,5) (see Table 2 and Figure 9).

The age distribution suggests that the majority of participants in the program are mid-career professionals, with relatively few younger individuals expressing interest. Given that the program was specifically designed for well-established professionals, this trend suggests that the participants have typically accumulated several years of experience in their respective fields, indicating a solid foundation of expertise.

Gender	Applied	Enrolled
	Percentage [%]	Percentage [%]
female	63,9	64,4
male	36,1	35,6
	100,0	100,0

Table 1: Gender Distribution

Figure 9: Age Distribution

Age	n	Minimum	Maximum	Average	Standard Deviation
Applicants	233	24	68	43,48	8,45
Participants	197	25	68	43,93	8,35

Table 2: Application Data Age Parameters

5.2.3 Nationality

People from approximately forty-five different countries applied for and enrolled in the RitrainPlus program. While the majority of applicants are from European countries, individuals from North America, South America, Australia, Africa, and Asia also participated. Notably, about one-third of the applicants are from Italy, around ten percent from Spain, eight percent from Portugal, five percent from France, and interestingly, eight percent from Romania.

Given the geographical context of the program, it is unsurprising that there is a higher level of interest from individuals in Europe, particularly Italy. The program predominantly focuses on the implementation of research infrastructure in an EU context, although some skills may be applicable in a broader context. However, the fact that participants have been drawn from around the world suggests that the online format of the program effectively enables global participation, regardless of participants' country of residence.

Figure 10: Geographical Location of Applicants

5.2.4 Professional Background

Most of the applicants and participants (about 65 percent) held a doctorate or a similar degree. About 30 percent had a master's degree or equivalent, while only about six percent held a bachelor's degree. More than half completed their studies in the field of natural sciences, over 15 percent in social sciences, and around ten percent in technical sciences, as well as in medicine and health. Only five percent studied humanities (see Table 3 and Table 4). A clear focus on natural sciences can be observed here, which may indicate a broader emphasis on this field within research and its associated infrastructures or suggest a stronger appeal to individuals from this field for the RitrainPlus program.

When looking at the interrelation between highest degree and discipline, it is noticeable that Natural Science and Medicine and Health show a higher rate of people with a doctoral degree, Social Sciences and Humanities a higher rate of people with a masters degree. For Medicine and Health, the lower number of bachelor's or master's degrees can be explained by the different structure of medical studies. Unlike other fields, medical education often follows a distinct system that does not align with the standard Bologna system of bachelor's and master's degrees.

Figure 11: Highest Degree by Discipline

Highest Degree and Discipline of Study		Social Sciences (n=37)	Humanities (n=12)	Natural Sciences (n=119)	Technical Sciences (n=24)	Medicine and Health (n=19)	Overall (n=211)
APPLICANTS							
Bachelors or similar level	Percentage	13,5%	8,3%	2,5%	16,7%	5,3%	6,6%
Masters or similar level	Percentage	51,4%	75,0%	21,0%	29,2%	15,8%	29,9%
Doctorate PHD or similar level	Percentage	35,1%	16,7%	76,5%	54,2%	78,9%	63,5%
	Percentage	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Table 3: Application Data Degree by Discipline Applicants

Highest Degree and Discipline of Study		Social Sciences (n=28)	Humanities (n=9)	Natural Sciences (n=101)	Technical Sciences (n=21)	Medicine and Health (n=18)	Overall (n=117)
PARTICIPANTS							
Bachelors or similar level	Percentage	14,3%	11,1%	2,0%	14,3%	5,6%	6,2%
Masters or similar level	Percentage	42,9%	66,7%	21,8%	33,3%	11,1%	27,7%
Doctorate PHD or similar level	Percentage	42,9%	22,2%	76,2%	52,4%	83,3%	66,1%
	Percentage	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%

Table 4: Application Data Degree by Discipline Participants

When looking at the fields in which these individuals are currently active, an even higher proportion (about two-thirds) are engaged in natural sciences. Additionally, around one-fifth of the people are active in the field of medicine and health, representing a higher number than those with an academic background in this discipline.¹

About two-thirds of the applicants and participants work in research infrastructure, while around 17 percent are involved with core facilities. Only a small number, under two percent, reported working in industry. Approximately half hold administrative positions, around 35 percent work in research, and about 13 percent are employed as technicians in their field.

Working in	Applied (n=62)	Enrolled (n=53)
	Percentage	Percentage
Social Sciences	6,5	7,5
Humanities	1,6	1,9
Natural Sciences	62,9	62,3
Technical Sciences	6,5	5,7
Medicine and life Sciences	22,6	22,6
Overall	100,0	100,0

Table 5: Application Data Active in Field

Type of Organisation	Applied (n=227)	Enrolled (n=193)
	Percentage	Percentage
Core Facility	17,2	17,6
Industry	1,3	1,6
Research Infrastructure	63,0	62,2
Other	18,5	18,7
	100,0	100,0

Table 6: Application Data Active in Organisation

¹ This number should be interpreted in the context that we have limited information about the specific fields the individuals are active in, compared to the information we have on their educational backgrounds.

Type of Position	Applied (n=213)	Enrolled (n=179)
	Percentage	Percentage
Research	34,7	35,8
Administrative Function	53,1	50,8
Technician	12,2	13,4
	100,0	100,0

Table 7: Application Data Type of Position

5.3. Interim Conclusion I: Target Group vs. Applicants

In summary, it can be said that the individuals interested in the program are predominantly women who are mid-career. A large portion of them work in the natural sciences, with another significant group in medicine. Fewer participants come from the fields of social sciences, humanities, or technical studies, with those working in social sciences and humanities being comparably lower educational level. Most of the applicants are employed in research infrastructure, with half holding administrative leadership roles. However, a considerable third is involved in research itself, and more than 10 percent work as technicians at institutions.

As previously mentioned, no definitive statement can be made regarding whether the proportion of women in the training program corresponds to their representation in the field of research infrastructure. However, it is well established that women are underrepresented in higher academic positions, despite having a greater presence in lower academic roles and often possessing higher qualifications. They receive less support and recruitment opportunities, have weaker professional networks, and face challenges in balancing private and professional responsibilities (Fritsch 2016). This suggests that women may be more reliant on training opportunities such as RltrainPlus to advance to higher positions within their respective organisations.

The analysis of the participants suggests that, in addition to age, qualifications and the type of organization indicate that these factors show the program is reaching the target audience for whom the courses are designed to some part. About two-thirds of the participants work in research infrastructure, and over 15 percent are in core facilities, making the program particularly relevant for well-established professionals in this field. However, it is notable that only 50 percent of the participants are engaged in administrative tasks. The courses, however, are specifically

tailored for individuals in management positions, aiming to enhance their skills in the role of mediators. But interestingly, there was a significant interest and demand from people outside these functions, who seem to be wanting to increase their knowledge concerning RI and CFs workings. This reveals a gap between the program's original target and the broader needs within the field.

Another notable finding was that the majority of interested individuals – nearly two-thirds – come from the natural sciences. The next largest group consists of professionals working in medicine or health science-related organizations. When examining the projects and landmarks listed in the ESFRI Roadmap 2021, it becomes evident that, when simply considering the number of projects (without taking size, structure, etc. into account), both Physical Sciences & Engineering and Health & Food sectors have the highest number of projects and landmarks, with 16 each included in the roadmap. However, it is important to note that the goal of these infrastructures is also to strengthen interdisciplinarity - as highlighted in the analysis of the Roadmap 2021 - and assigning the infrastructures to only one field seems insufficient to adequately represent the full scope and interdisciplinary nature of the infrastructures (ESFRI, 2021). Nevertheless, the application to professionals in the natural sciences appears to be particularly strong in comparison and this imbalance has to be considered moving forward.

Has the Target Group Been Reached?

- ✓ ~80 % working with Research Infrastructure or Core Facilities
- ✓ ~50 % in administrative or management positions
- ✓ Mainly mid-career (3/4 between 35 and 54)

- ✗ ~ 50 % in research or technicians

- High rate of women
- High rate of natural sciences

5.4. Course Participation

The program offered participants the opportunity to select from a range of seven courses tailored to the needs of professionals working in Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Core Facilities (CFs).

Participants could choose from the following courses:

1. **Managing the Lifecycle of an Research Infrastructure (RI):** Exploring the stages of an RI's lifecycle, from planning to decommissioning.
2. **Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) in RIs and CFs:** Addressing key ethical, legal, and societal challenges in science.
3. **Data Management:** Building skills for defining and implementing data management policies.
4. **Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Engagement with Industry:** Fostering collaboration and innovation between research and industry.
5. **Socio-economic Impact of RIs:** Measuring the broader socio-economic benefits and costs of RIs.
6. **Team Building and Development:** Developing cohesive and high-performing research teams.
7. **Coaching Development Programme:** Enhancing leadership and mentoring capabilities for RI managers.

The following results provide an overview of the participation rates and offer detailed insights into the professional backgrounds and profiles of those who enrolled in each course.

Two-thirds of the participants chose to take only one course during the period from 2023 to 2024. About one-quarter attended two courses, while only a small number opted for more than two (see Table 8). This would suggest that participants choose specific courses tailored to their particular training needs in their respective positions. Notably, participants often applied for more courses than they ultimately attended, contradicting this initial assumption and rather indicating that organizational difficulties made attending additional courses challenging. When working full-time, managing additional training can be difficult to organize and reconcile with daily life.

The course that garnered the most interest was '*Managing the Lifecycle of an RI*', taken by approximately 30 percent of participants. This course discusses the lifecycle from the design

phase to implementation, touching on different organizational levels. Because of this broad scope, the course could appeal to a wide range of positions in RIS and would be useful for gaining a general understanding of the process, as well as attract individuals who are not very familiar with the dynamics. 'Data Management' followed closely, with about 28 percent participation. The courses 'Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications,' 'Team Building and Development,' 'Innovation and Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry' and 'Socio-economic Impact of RIS' each attracted between 20 and 25 percent of participants. In contrast, 'Coaching Development Programme' saw less interest, with under 10 percent participation (see Table 10). This course offering is strongly focused on interpersonal skills and empathy, with a less prominent emphasis on RIS itself. Instead, it concentrates more on general interpersonal dynamics and discourse culture, suggesting that people interested in the program would rather opt for RIS-specific skills

A noticeably larger proportion of participants combined the 'Data Management' course with 'Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Engagement with Industry' course, as well as the 'Team Building and Development' course with the 'Coaching Development Programme' The latter combination points to managers, wanting to specifically improve their management and team-leading skills.

Overall, the courses had a higher participation count in 2023 than in 2024. Only 'Socio-economic Impact of RIS' did generate a higher enrollment rate in 2024 than the year before.

Number of courses	Absolute Frequencies	Percentage [%]
1	135	67,8
2	48	24,1
3	6	3,0
4 or more	10	5,0
Overall	199	100,0

Table 8: Application Data Number of Courses enrolled in

Number of courses	
n	199
Average	1,5628
Mode	1,00

Table 9: Application Data Average Number of Courses

Enrolment Rate			
	n	Percentage	Percentage of Participants
Coaching Development	17	5,5%	8,5%
Ethical, Legal and Social Implications	45	14,5%	22,6%
Managing the Lifecycle	63	20,3%	31,7%
Team Building and Development	42	13,5%	21,1%
Data Management	55	17,7%	27,6%
Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement	48	15,4%	24,1%
Socio Economic Impact	41	13,2%	20,6%
Overall	311	100,0%	156,3%

Table 10: Application Data Course Enrolment

5.4.1 Coaching Development Programme

Overall, 8,5 percent of the individuals participating in the program attended the ‘*Coaching Development Programme*’ course. A relatively high number of participants expressed interest in the course but ultimately did not attend.

Relatively more women were interested in the course than men. More than three quarter of the attending were female. Moreover, this course was more popular among individuals with higher educational degrees as well as people in an administrative position. We also see a relatively larger amount of people in medicine and health participating in this course, whereas people working in natural science were less interested. There can be no definite interpretation of why this course was chosen by this specific target group, but it indicates that women, as well as people working in medicine and health, show a stronger interest in developing interpersonal skills.²

Coaching Development Programme	Frequency	Percentage [%]
applied, but not enrolled	15	7,5
enrolled in 2023	10	5,0
enrolled in 2024	7	3,5
not enrolled or applied	167	83,9
Overall	199	100,0

Table 11: Application Data Course Enrolment Coaching and Development Programme

Coaching Development Programme		Not Enrolled	Enrolled	Overall
Female (n=125)	Percentage	62,2%	76,7% ↑	64,4%
Male (n=69)	Percentage	37,8%	23,3%	35,6%
Bachelor’s or similar level (n=11)	Percentage	7,0%	0,0% ↓	5,9%
Master’s or similar level (n=54)	Percentage	29,9%	23,3%	28,9%
Doctorate, PHD or similar level (n=122)	Percentage	63,1%	76,7% ↑	65,2%
Social Sciences (n=4)	Percentage	8,3%	0,0%	7,5%
Humanities (n=1)	Percentage	2,1%	0,0%	1,9%
Natural Science (n=33)	Percentage	66,7%	20,0%	62,3%
Technical Science (n=3)	Percentage	4,2%	20,0%	5,7%
Medicine or Health Science (n=12)	Percentage	18,8%	60,0% ↑	22,6%
Research (n=64)	Percentage	38,9%	20,0%	35,8%
Administrative Function (n=91)	Percentage	47,7%	66,7%	50,8%
Technician (n=24)	Percentage	13,4%	13,3%	13,4%

Table 12: Application Data Enrolment Coaching Development Programme by Background

² Interpretations based on the descriptive analysis must be made with caution due to the limited case numbers.

5.4.2 Ethical, Legal and Social Implications in RIs and CFs

The ‘*Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications in RIs and CFs*’ course was well-attended, with over 20 percent of participants enrolling. Notably, most individuals who applied also followed through and completed the course.

A higher percentage of women expressed interest in this course, with around 73 percent of the participants being female. Additionally, 8,9 percent of the participants have a bachelor's degree or a similar qualification, which is comparably high. Furthermore, only a relatively low number of technicians enrolled.

Ethical, Legal and Social Implications	Frequency	Percentage [%]
applied, but not enrolled	5	2,5
enrolled in 2023	31	15,6
enrolled in 2024	14	7,0
not enrolled or applied	149	74,9
Overall	199	100,0

Table 13: Application Data Course Enrolment Ethical, Legal and Social Implications in RIs and CFs

Ethical, Legal and Social Implications		Not enrolled	Enrolled	Overall
Female (n=125)	Percentage	61,6%	72,9% ↑	64,4%
Male (n=69)	Percentage	38,4%	27,1%	35,6%
Bachelor's or similar level (n=11)	Percentage	4,9%	8,9% ↑	5,9%
Master's or similar level (n=54)	Percentage	30,3%	24,4%	28,9%
Doctorate, PHD or similar level (n=122)	Percentage	64,8%	66,7%	65,2%
Social Sciences (n=4)	Percentage	4,9%	16,7%	7,5%
Humanities (n=1)	Percentage	2,4%	0,0%	1,9%
Natural Science (n=33)	Percentage	65,9%	50,0%	62,3%
Technical Science (n=3)	Percentage	4,9%	8,3%	5,7%
Medicine or Health Science (n=12)	Percentage	22,0%	25,0%	22,6%
Research (n=64)	Percentage	35,0%	38,1%	35,8%
Administrative Function (n=91)	Percentage	50,4%	52,4%	50,8%
Technician (n=24)	Percentage	14,6%	9,5% ↓	13,4%

Table 14: Application Data Enrolment Rate Ethical, Legal and Social Implications in RIs and CFs by Background

5.4.3 Managing the Lifecycle of an Research Infrastructure

About one third of the participants enrolled in ‘*Managing the lifecycle of an RI*’, making it the highest-enrolled course. The participant rate remained approximately the same in 2023 and 2024.

This course also seems to be more appealing to women as well as people with rather high qualifications, with around three quarters having a PHD or similar degree. This does not support the initial suggestion of explaining the high participation rate by the broad accessibility for people from all backgrounds. Instead, there seems to be a noticeably higher interest among individuals with higher academic qualifications. However, in general, the type of position is broadly represented.

Managing the Lifecycle	Frequency	Percentage [%]
applied, but not enrolled	12	6,0
enrolled in 2023	33	16,6
enrolled in 2024	30	15,1
not enrolled or applied	124	62,3
Overall	199	100,0

Table 15: Application Data Course Enrolment Managing the Lifecycle of an RI

Managing the Lifecycle		Not enrolled	Enrolled	Overall
Female (n=125)	Percentage	61,5%	69,4% ↑	64,4%
Male (n=69)	Percentage	38,5%	30,6%	35,6%
Bachelor’s or similar level (n=11)	Percentage	8,5%	1,4%	5,9%
Master’s or similar level (n=54)	Percentage	32,2%	23,2%	28,9%
Doctorate, PHD or similar level (n=122)	Percentage	59,3%	75,4% ↑	65,2%
Social Sciences (n=4)	Percentage	6,3%	9,5%	7,5%
Humanities (n=1)	Percentage	0,0%	4,8%	1,9%
Natural Science (n=33)	Percentage	59,4%	66,7%	62,3%
Technical Science (n=3)	Percentage	9,4%	0,0%	5,7%
Medicine or Health Science (n=12)	Percentage	25,0%	19,0%	22,6%
Research (n=64)	Percentage	33,9%	38,8%	35,8%
Administrative Function (n=91)	Percentage	51,8%	49,3%	50,8%
Technician (n=24)	Percentage	14,3%	11,9%	13,4%

Table 16: Application Data Enrolment Rate Managing the Lifecycle of an RI by Background

5.4.4 Team Building and Development

Just under 30 percent of participants showed interest in the ‘*Team Building and Development*’ course, and slightly over 20 percent of them ultimately enrolled in it.

Again, we see a higher interest rate among female participants with over three quarter of the people enrolling being female. This course appeals more to people with a comparable lower degree on a bachelor’s level compared to the general share. Interestingly, there is still a high percentage of people in administrative positions. This aligns with the course content, which focuses on specific management and administrative skills.

Team Building and Development	Frequency	Percentage [%]
applied, but not enrolled	13	6,5
enrolled in 2023	26	13,1
enrolled in 2024	16	8,0
not enrolled or applied	144	72,4
Overall	199	100,0

Table 17: Application Data Course Enrolment Team Building and Development

Team Building and Development		Not enrolled	Enrolled	Overall
Female (n=125)	Percentage	59,9%	76,9% ↑	64,4%
Male (n=69)	Percentage	40,1%	23,1%	35,6%
Bachelor’s or similar level (n=11)	Percentage	4,4%	10,0% ↑	5,9%
Master’s or similar level (n=54)	Percentage	29,9%	26,0%	28,9%
Doctorate, PHD or similar level (n=122)	Percentage	65,7%	64,0%	65,2%
Social Sciences (n=4)	Percentage	9,8%	0,0%	7,5%
Humanities (n=1)	Percentage	2,4%	0,0%	1,9%
Natural Science (n=33)	Percentage	58,5%	75,0%	62,3%
Technical Science (n=3)	Percentage	2,4%	16,7%	5,7%
Medicine or Health Science (n=12)	Percentage	26,8%	8,3%	22,6%
Research (n=64)	Percentage	36,9%	32,7%	35,8%
Administrative Function (n=91)	Percentage	48,5%	57,1% ↑	50,8%
Technician (n=24)	Percentage	14,6%	10,2%	13,4%

Table 18: Application Data Enrolment Rate Team Building and Development by Background

5.4.5 Data Management

About 28 percent of the participants enrolled in the ‘Data Management’ course. An additional 15 percent showed initial interest but did not end up enrolling.

For this course, male participants showed somewhat higher interest, with a little under 40 percent of the participants being male. Notably, there seems to be a higher interest among program participants with a bachelor’s degree and a lower interest to those with a higher degree on the level of an PHD. Additionally, there was a significantly higher interest rate among technicians, making up 20 percent of the people enrolled in this course.

Furthermore, people from social sciences show a stronger interest in this course compared to others, while individuals in natural sciences show less interest.

Data Management	Frequency	Percentage [%]
applied, but not enrolled	28	14,1
enrolled in 2023	31	15,6
enrolled in 2024	24	12,1
enrolled in 2024 and 2023	1	0,5
not enrolled or applied	115	57,8
Overall	199	100,0

Table 19: Application Data Course Enrolment Data Management

Data Management		Not enrolled	Enrolled	Overall
Female (n=125)	Percentage	67,0%	61,0%	64,4%
Male (n=69)	Percentage	33,0%	39,0% ↑	35,6%
Bachelor’s or similar level (n=11)	Percentage	4,5%	7,8%	5,9%
Master’s or similar level (n=54)	Percentage	28,2%	29,9%	28,9%
Doctorate, PHD or similar level (n=122)	Percentage	67,3%	62,3% ↓	65,2%
Social Sciences (n=4)	Percentage	3,4%	12,5% ↑	7,5%
Humanities (n=1)	Percentage	0,0%	4,2%	1,9%
Natural Science (n=33)	Percentage	69,0%	54,2% ↓	62,3%
Technical Science (n=3)	Percentage	6,9%	4,2%	5,7%
Medicine or Health Science (n=12)	Percentage	20,7%	25,0%	22,6%
Research (n=64)	Percentage	37,5%	33,3%	35,8%
Administrative Function (n=91)	Percentage	53,8%	46,7%	50,8%
Technician (n=24)	Percentage	8,7%	20,0% ↑	13,4%

Table 20: Application Data Enrolment Rate Data Management by Background

5.4.6 Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engaging with Industry

Just under a quarter of the participants enrolled in the ‘*Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Engagement with Industry*’ course. An additional 10 percent showed interest but did not end up enrolling.

For this course, the participants are relatively highly qualified, with a higher percentage holding a doctoral or similar degree and working in administrative roles. Additionally, we observe that individuals working in medicine or health sciences are comparatively more represented in this course.

Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engaging	Frequency	Percentage [%]
applied, but not enrolled	19	9,5
enrolled in 2023	27	13,6
enrolled in 2024	21	10,6
not enrolled or applied	132	66,3
Overall	199	100,0

Table 21: Application Data Course Enrolment Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engaging with Industry

Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engaging		Not enrolled	Enrolled	Overall
Female (n=125)	Percentage	63,3%	66,7%	64,4%
Male (n=69)	Percentage	36,7%	33,3%	35,6%
Bachelor’s or similar level (n=11)	Percentage	6,3%	4,9%	5,9%
Master’s or similar level (n=54)	Percentage	32,5%	21,3%	28,9%
Doctorate, PHD or similar level (n=122)	Percentage	61,1%	73,8% ↑	65,2%
Social Sciences (n=4)	Percentage	10,5%	0,0%	7,5%
Humanities (n=1)	Percentage	2,6%	0,0%	1,9%
Natural Science (n=33)	Percentage	63,2%	60,0%	62,3%
Technical Science (n=3)	Percentage	5,3%	6,7%	5,7%
Medicine or Health Science (n=12)	Percentage	18,4%	33,3% ↑	22,6%
Research (n=64)	Percentage	42,0%	23,3%	35,8%
Administrative Function (n=91)	Percentage	44,5%	63,3% ↑	50,8%
Technician (n=24)	Percentage	13,4%	13,3%	13,4%

Table 22: Application Data Enrolment Rate Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry by Background

5.4.7 Socio-economic Impact of RIs

Just around one-fifth of the participants enrolled in the ‘Socio-economic Impact of RIs’ course, with an additional 7 percent showing interest.

A rather high rate of 62 percent of the participants in the ‘*Socio-Economic Impact of RIs*’ course were people working in administrative positions. Additionally, a big percentage of people working in social sciences showed interest in this course. But we see a smaller rate of people with higher degrees on a PHD level enrolling. The higher interest of individuals with a background in social sciences can be explained by the course's thematic emphasis.

Socio Economic Impact	Frequency	Percentage [%]
applied, but not enrolled	14	7,0
enrolled in 2023	18	9,0
enrolled in 2024	23	11,6
not enrolled or applied	144	72,4
Overall	199	100,0

Table 23: Application Data Course Enrolment Socio-economic Impact of RIs

Socio Economic Impact		Not enrolled	Enrolled	Overall
Female (n=125)	Percentage	64,5%	64,2%	64,4%
Male (n=69)	Percentage	35,5%	35,8%	35,6%
Bachelor’s or similar level (n=11)	Percentage	5,8%	6,1%	5,9%
Master’s or similar level (n=54)	Percentage	27,5%	32,7%	28,9%
Doctorate, PHD or similar level (n=122)	Percentage	66,7%	61,2% ↑	65,2%
Social Sciences (n=4)	Percentage	2,4%	25,0% ↑	7,5%
Humanities (n=1)	Percentage	2,4%	0,0%	1,9%
Natural Science (n=33)	Percentage	65,9%	50,0%	62,3%
Technical Science (n=3)	Percentage	4,9%	8,3%	5,7%
Medicine or Health Science (n=12)	Percentage	24,4%	16,7%	22,6%
Research (n=64)	Percentage	40,3%	24,0%	35,8%
Administrative Function (n=91)	Percentage	46,5%	62,0% ↑	50,8%
Technician (n=24)		13,2%	14,0%	13,4%

Table 24: Application Data Enrolment Rate Socio-economic Impact of RIs by Background

5.5. Interim Conclusion 2: Target Group and Course Participation

Summarizing the results of these analyses, we can first observe that the generally higher interest of women in the program, is even more pronounced in the courses *‘Coaching Development Programme’*, *‘Ethical, Legal and Social Implications in RIs and CFs’*, *‘Managing the Lifecycle of an RI’*, and *‘Team Building and Development’*. In contrast, the course *‘Data Management’* has a comparatively higher proportion of men. The courses chosen predominantly by women focus on interpersonal skills, ethical considerations, and organizational development. In contrast, the *‘Data Management’* course, which is selected by a higher proportion of men, emphasizes analytical skills.

A high number of participants in the *‘Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry’* course come from the field of medicine or health sciences. This suggests that professionals working in research infrastructures (RIs) and core facilities within these domains recognize the growing need for entrepreneurial skills. Given the increasing emphasis on translational research and technology transfer, professionals in these fields may seek to develop competencies in innovation management and establishing relations with the industry. In contrast *‘Socio-Economic Impact of RIs’* course attracts a higher rate of participants from the social sciences. This trend may indicate that professionals working in RIs and core facilities with a social science background are particularly engaged in assessing the broader implications of scientific infrastructures.³

When examining the qualifications and positions of participants enrolling in different courses, the *‘Coaching Development Programme’* and *‘Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry’* appear to effectively reach the intended target audience of the RitrainPlus program—well-established professionals in management roles. This is reflected in the higher proportion of participants with advanced academic qualifications who hold administrative or managerial positions within research infrastructures and core facilities. Similarly, *‘Socio-Economic Impact of Research Infrastructures’* and *‘Team Building and Development’* also attract a significant number of administrative and managerial professionals; however, participants in these courses tend to have a slightly lower level of academic qualification. In contrast, *‘Data Management’* strongly appeals to professionals working as technicians within their institutions,

³ These interpretations must be approached with caution, as the recorded fields of activity contain only very small sample sizes.

indication a discrepancy regarding the intended target group. It seems that the technical focus of the course is more appealing to technical staff and is less aligned with the interests of individuals in managerial or organizational roles.

In this evaluation, we assessed whether the target group—professionals in infrastructure management positions or those aiming for such roles—was effectively reached. While just over 50 percent of participants hold administrative positions, a significant portion of the remaining individuals are in scientific or technical roles. However, there is the high level of academic qualifications among the participants. This could suggest that some of these individuals are not yet in administrative positions but are using the program as a stepping stone to advance and take on management responsibilities.

Notably, the courses ‘*Coaching Development Programme*’ and ‘*Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry*’⁴ were particularly successful in reaching this target group, fulfilling their needs and expectations. These courses appear well-tailored to the career development of professionals aiming for leadership roles in research infrastructures.

However, when analysing the ‘*Data Management*’ course, a distinct trend emerges: it attracted a different target group than originally anticipated. The participants in this course seem to have a different professional background or focus, which may indicate a mismatch between the course content and the intended audience of infrastructure management professionals.

Which Courses Attract the Target Audience?

Management professionals with advanced degrees:

- ✓ *Coaching and Innovation*
- ✓ *Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Research Infrastructure and Core Facilities*

Management professionals:

- ✓ *Socio-Economic Impact of Research Infrastructures*
- ✓ *Team Building and Development*

⁴ For admission to this course, participants have to be registered PhD students in the Third Cycle of the University or Managers and Operators of Ris and CFs.

6 Course Assessments

In 2023, a short feedback loop was conducted to evaluate the courses, using a guideline consisting of 20 questions. Sixteen of these questions employed a rating system ranging from 0 to 10, while the remaining four were open-ended. The courses evaluated were *'Data Management'*, *'Ethical, Legal and Social Implications'*, *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry'*, *'Managing the lifecycle of an RI'* and *'Socio-economic Impact of RIs'*. This section briefly presents the results of this feedback evaluation. It is important to note, however, that only a very small number of participants provided evaluations. Depending on the course, the number of responses ranged from 3 to 11. Besides the overall assessment of the course, questions addressed the choice of topics, their relevance, and professional benefits, as well as the practical applicability and the execution of these topics in the context of teaching. Additionally, the organization, infrastructure, and support surrounding the course offerings were evaluated.

6.1 General Feedback Results

In general, the courses received positive feedback, with the *'Ethical, Legal and Social Implications'* course receiving the highest ratings, while *'Managing the Lifecycle of an RI'* was rated the lowest. Participants expressed strong satisfaction with the chosen content, particularly highlighting the relevance of the topics to the management needs of RIs or CFs. However, ratings were lower regarding the expected professional benefits of the course. Regarding the execution during the lessons, feedback for most courses was generally very positive. The only area receiving comparatively lower ratings was the effectiveness in meeting participants' educational expectations. In contrast, participants were very satisfied with the quality of teaching and the responsiveness of the instructors. Feedback on the infrastructure and organization was generally positive. However, clarity regarding the course structure, expectations, and assignments received slightly more critical feedback.

	n=	Data Management	Ethical, Legal and Social Implications	Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement	Managing the Lifecycle of an RI	Socio-economic Impact	Mean
1. How would you rate your OVERALL satisfaction with this course?	6	7,00	8,60	8,36	6,00	7,88	7,57
2. Contents (topics, relevance for RIs/CFs current or prospective operators, professional benefits...)	5	7,17	8,60	8,82	8,67	8,38	8,33
3. Delivery (quality of teaching and course materials)	11	7,67	8,40	7,91	8,00	7,00	7,80
4. Service (online infrastructures, administrative staff and support services)	3	6,33	8,60	7,18	7,67	7,75	7,51
5. Relevance of topics covered to RI's/CFs management needs	8	8,17	8,40	8,55	8,00	8,63	8,35
6. Balance between theory and practice		7,33	8,40	7,36	4,33	6,38	6,76
7. Clarity of module structure, expectations and assignments		7,50	8,40	6,27	3,67	7,63	6,69
8. Effectiveness in meeting your educational expectations for this course		5,50	8,40	7,64	4,33	7,25	6,62
9. Expected professional benefits		5,83	7,80	7,91	5,00	7,50	6,81
10. Quality of teaching / teaching (consider the most representative case when lectures are given by several different Teachers)		8,67	8,20	7,82	8,00	7,63	8,06
11. Quality of course materials (overall)		7,83	8,40	7,91	8,00	6,88	7,80
12. Usefulness of cases, exercises and assignments in learning how to apply the concepts		7,50	8,40	8,36	4,33	7,00	7,12
13. Instructors' responsiveness to participant questions		9,00	8,60	8,64	8,33	8,75	8,66
14. Appropriateness of the pace at which topics were covered		7,67	7,80	7,82	6,33	8,00	7,52
15. Quality of online infrastructure (learning platform, webinars, etc.)		8,17	8,60	6,55	8,00	8,38	7,94
16. Support and service offered by Administrative and Technical staff		8,33	8,60	7,09	7,67	8,00	7,94
Overall assesment ratings		7,48	8,39	7,76	6,65	7,69	7,59

Content and Topics / Practical Applicability / Execution of Content / Infrastructure and Organization

Table 25: Course Feedback Data Average Ratings

Overall, the courses were rated positively, though there were indications of areas for improvement, particularly concerning the professional benefits, alignment with educational expectations, and clarity of course structure. This suggests that people perceive the discussed topics as highly relevant to the field and consider them well taught. However, they do not seem to believe that these topics translate well into their actual careers and work experiences. This indicates a contradiction between course content and its practical application or suggests a mismatch in the target group, as participants may not be in the right positions to apply the knowledge effectively.

However, due to the low number of participants, these results should be interpreted with caution, as they provide insights into potential issues rather than definitive conclusions about the general reception of the courses.

6.2 Interim Conclusion 3: Content – Course Feedback

Comparing these results with the feedback from course-specific participants, we can see that the course on *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Engagement with Industry'* received rather positive feedback, especially concerning the content as well the career opportunities expected from this course, which were rated the highest. This indicates a good alignment of the expectation of the reached target audience with the course objective. In contrast, the *'Data Management'* course, which likely attracted a different group of participants than originally intended, performed less well in these areas. Interestingly the combination of *'Data Management'* and *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Engagement with Industry'* was quite popular, indicating some kind of overlap between those two course audiences.

Ultimately, we can identify initial indicators in the overall evaluation of the courses suggesting that they were well received, particularly in terms of content. Moreover, specifically the target group appears to be satisfied with the course outcomes, concerning content and applicability.

However, these conclusions should be seen more as indicators rather than definitive results. Due to the challenging data situation regarding course feedback, no firm conclusions can be drawn. Only a small number of people responded to the invitation to provide feedback on the courses. It is possible that those who did respond had stronger opinions, which motivated them to provide feedback, or held differing opinions from the overall population. To support initial deductions, surveys and interviews will continue to be used to examine those dynamics.

How Are These Courses Rated by the Target

- Overall positive feedback
- Positive feedback on the content of target group-aligned courses
- Slightly more critical feedback on content of courses less relevant to the target group

7 Survey on Participants Perspectives and Attitudes

This chapter presents the analysis of a survey conducted between late 2024 and early 2025, specifically developed and conducted for the evaluation of the RitrainPlus program. The survey aimed to gather comprehensive insights from participants, covering key dimensions such as:

- **Socioeconomic background**
- **Professional background**
- **Motivation and aspirations**
- **Self-efficacy**
- **Opinions on Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Core Facilities (CFs)**
- **Course selection and preferences**
- **Assessment of the program and individual courses**

By examining these aspects, the survey provides valuable context to support and expand upon findings from the application data and course feedback.

7.1 Methodology

The survey is based on a questionnaire that was designed around key themes and hypotheses related to the program's objectives. The questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure its reliability and clarity before distribution.

The survey was distributed to all participants of the program, making it a full census rather than a sample-based approach. To maximize participation, survey links were sent at multiple points in time throughout December 2024 and January 2025. Out of 199 program participants (which were selected from 233 applicants), 74 responded, yielding a response rate of approximately 37.2 percent. While the sample size is limited, the responses still provide valuable insights into participants' experiences and perspectives. The smaller sample size was taken into account during the analysis and interpretation of the results and should be considered when reading the report.

Demographic information was collected to understand the background of the participants, such as professional field, career stage, and prior experience with research infrastructures (RIs) and core facilities (CFs).

To gain a better insight into the survey sample, the distribution of socio-economic data in the sample is compared to the distribution in the applicant population.

The collected data was analysed using SPSS, applying descriptive statistical methods (e.g., distribution, mean, standard deviation) to summarize key findings regarding the professional background, aspirations, motivations, and evaluations of the program and courses. Additionally, correlation analyses were conducted to explore relationships between relevant variables, such as the participants' background and their evaluation of specific courses.

While the response rate was moderate, the analysis offers meaningful insights into the experiences of participants, though potential non-response bias must be considered when interpreting the findings.

7.2 Survey Sample – Data Quality

In the following section, the achieved sample is introduced and compared with the distribution of the applicant population. This analysis provides insights into the composition and structure of our sample, highlighting any potential biases or deviations. Specifically, we examine whom we reached with the survey and assess how representative our participants are in relation to the overall applicant pool.

Compared to all applicants of the program the survey sample shows a more balanced distribution between men and women. Among the population of applicants and participants presented earlier, a higher proportion of women can be observed (see Table 26). This suggests a slight non-response error, with feedback less frequently provided by women. In terms of age, the distribution is similar, with a concentration of middle-aged individuals. However, the 35 to 44 age group is more prominently represented in the survey sample (see Table 27). Compared to the population of applicants, participants in the survey have a slightly lower average level of education (see Table 28).

In the survey, there is a higher representation of individuals from the natural sciences - who are already quite prominent in the application data - and a lower representation of individuals from technical fields compared to the overall applicant population. Additionally, the survey included the option "Agriculture," which was not used in the classification of the overall population (see Table 29).

Overall, we can observe a slight deviation between the group that participated in the survey and all individuals who applied for the program. Unlike the registration data, the survey data may be influenced by selection bias. Participation was voluntary, which could lead to distortions between

the (gross) sample, which includes all participants, and the net sample, where data are only available for those who actually responded. Primarily, there is a difference in gender, along with a slight redistribution in age and educational background. However, the survey successfully reached individuals with diverse backgrounds, covering a wide range of participants to draw meaningful conclusions.

Gender	Program Applicants (n=227)	Survey Participants (n=66)
	Percentage [%]	Percentage [%]
Female	63,9	51,5
Male	36,1	47,0
Non-Binary	/	1,5
	100,0	100,0

Table 26: Survey Data & Application Data Gender Distribution

Age	Program Applicants (n=227)	Survey Participants (n=68)
	Percentage [%]	Percentage [%]
under 25	0,4	0,0
25 to 34	15,0	16,7
35 to 44	40,3	45,5
45 to 54	32,6	25,8
55 to 64	11,2	12,1
65 or older	0,4	0,0
	100,0	100,0

Table 27: Survey Data & Application Data Age Distribution

Highest Degree	Program Applicants (n=222)	Survey Participants (n=68)
	Percentage [%]	Percentage [%]
Bachelor's or similar level	6,3	7,4
Master's or similar level	30,6	33,8
Post-master's Certificate	/	4,4
Doctorate PHD or similar level	63,1	54,4
	100,0	100,0

Table 28: Survey Data & Application Data Highest Degree

Degree in	Program Applicants (n=218)	Survey Participants (n=67)
	Percentage [%]	Percentage [%]
Natural Sciences	55,0	59,7
Medical and Health Sciences	9,2	9,0
Engineering and Technology	11,9	4,5
Humanities	6,0	6,0
Social Sciences	17,9	14,9
Agricultural Sciences	/	6,0
	100,0	100,0

Table 29: Survey Data and Application Data Discipline

7.3 Target Group

The following section examines the professional background of the participants and analyzes how well these align with the program's target group, providing a basis for later analyses.

Most people work with research infrastructure or core facilities. However, a significant number around 15 percent are not affiliated with research infrastructure or core facilities and do not seem to fit the target group (see Table 30 and Figure 12: Affiliations to RIs and CFs). The interest of this group in the RitrainPlus program could be explained by a past or an upcoming involvement with RIs or CFs. If this does not apply, there is a clear contradiction, between the intent of the program - offering training for RI and Cf professionals – and the effective application of the program.

Slightly more than half of the respondents work for a higher education institution, indicating their involvement in academic structures (see Table 30). 45 percent of the sample hold a temporary position, while 55 percent have a permanent post (see Table 31).

Almost 60 percent of those working in research infrastructures (RI) or core facilities (CF) have notably rather limited experience in this specific field, having worked in it for five years or less. One-fifth have been involved in RI or CF for between six and ten years, while another fifth have worked in the field for longer (see Table 32). Since the courses target established professionals in the field with a certain level of expected experience, this suggests a potential mismatch between the course audience and their actual expertise.

The sample reflects previously observed trends, showing a high proportion of individuals working in natural sciences, accounting for nearly 65 percent of respondents. Additionally, a significant share—almost 20 percent—are employed in medical and health-related institutions. Engineering and technology are represented by around five percent, while social sciences make up seven percent. Humanities and agricultural sciences are represented to an even lesser extent (see Table 33).

A large proportion of the sample consists of individuals in management positions, making up 40 percent. However, an even greater share—around 42 percent—are part of the scientific staff, working in both research and non-research-related roles (see Table 34). Even though we see a categorization as scientific staff, this does not necessarily mean that no administrative roles are carried out.

This supposition is backed up when looking at the supervisory duties: Two-thirds of the sample are involved in roles where they take on responsibilities as team leaders (see Table 35).

Currently employed at or associated with	Percentage [%]
an University or Institution of Higher Education (n=64)	54,7
a Research Infrastructure or Core Facility (n=64)	84,4

Table 30: Survey Data Working with RI and CFs or / in Academia

Figure 12: Affiliations to RIs and CFs

Type Employment (n=60)	Percentage [%]
time limited, temporary post	45,0
permanent or tenured post	55,0
	100,0

Table 31: Survey Data Type of Employment

Work experience in RI or CF (n=54)	Percentage [%]
5 years or less	59,3
6-10 years	20,4
11-15 years	16,7
16-20 years	1,9
21 years or more	1,9
	100,0

Table 32: Survey Data Work experience

Area of Work (n=57)	Percentage [%]
Natural Sciences	64,9
Medical and Health Sciences	19,3
Engineering and Technology	5,3
Humanities	1,8
Social Sciences	7,0
Agricultural Sciences	1,8
	100,0

Table 33: Survey Data Area of Work

Role at RI or CF (n=52)	Percentage [%]
Non-scientific, Non-technical Staff	1,9
Technician	5,8
Scientific Staff (research related)	25,0
Scientific Staff (non-research related)	17,3
Management and Business Operations	40,4
Administrative Staff	9,6
	100,0

Table 34: Survey Data Role at Work

Team Leader (=62)	Percentage
Management Responsibilities	66,1
No management Responsibilities	33,9
	100,0

Table 35: Survey Data Team Leader

7.4 Interim Conclusion 4: Representation of Target Group

In this sample, we observe a stronger shift away from the intended target group of the course program. Only 40 percent are in management positions, and most have no more than five years of experience in the field. This could indicate a potential bias in the sample compared to the overall population of program participants.

Figure 13: Target Group

7.5 Descriptive Analysis of Survey

In this section, the perspectives and attitudes of the participants are examined descriptively. Despite the small sample size, these are presented using the mean rather than the mode, as the mean allows for a more nuanced understanding of response patterns. In this specific context, the mode would not provide the same level of detail in capturing variations in participants' answers.

Firstly, the motivations for participants to join the program is presented. They rated statements on a scale from one to five, with 1 indicating no resonance and 5 indicating a high level of resonance.

The main reasons respondents participated in the program are their desires to learn new tasks and challenge themselves. The desire to learn new tasks has an average around 4,5 with quite a small standard deviation, meaning most of the participants agreed on this being a major motivator for participation. Factors such as task failure or social expectations appear to be less relevant to the participants. Participants also felt some kind of professional or organizational expectations to take part in the program, both averaging around 2,5 (see Figure 14). This response pattern suggests strong intrinsic motivation to join the program.

When analysing participants' motivation to join the program based on their work experience and background (see Figure 15), we see that the desire to learn new tasks remains a consistently high motivator across all groups, regardless of their professional background. Seeking challenges appears to be less relevant for well-established professionals in the field, whereas professionals with less work experience in the field still rate the motivation through seeking challenges higher. More experienced show a slightly higher average when asked about fear of task failure as a motivating factor, though with a relatively high standard deviation. This means that some highly established professionals are afraid of not being able to live up to their responsibilities, while this seems less of a concern for less established individuals. Additionally, there seem to be a stronger experienced expectations placed on those established professionals in management positions regarding their participation in the program. This means that for people in higher positions, participation in RltrainPlus is more strongly driven by professional pressure than for those in lower positions. That being said, organizational expectations and task failure still remain relatively low as motivating factors when compared to intrinsic motivations.

Participants were also asked about their career-related expectations for the program. Statements on expectations concerning their career advancements were rated on a scale from 1 to 5.

The highest average agreement rate, nearly 4, with a relatively small standard deviation of around 0.9, pertains to the statement "enhancing my leadership and decision-making skills in the position I am currently holding." This strongly aligns with the program's objectives, which aim to improve these specific skills, especially concerning courses like *'Team Building and Development'* or *'Coaching Development Program'*. The goal of advancing one's career and achieving higher positions was rated around 3.5, while the goal of achieving management roles specifically was rated around 3.3. This could be explained by the fact that a significant number of participants are already in management positions.

Looking at the background-specific responses (Table 17), we see that people in management positions within RIs or CFs have a stronger motivation to use the program to advance their careers and achieve higher positions. They also place greater emphasis on enhancing their leadership and decision-making skills. Achieving management positions is a primary goal for individuals not working in RI or CFs.

Motivation for Participating in the Program

Figure 14: Survey Data Motivation for Participating in RltrainPlus

Motivation for Participating in the Program (Group-based)

Figure 15 Survey Data Motivation by Target Group

Career Advancement

Figure 16: Survey Data Expected Career Advancement

Career Advancement (Group-based)

Figure 17: Survey Data Expected Career Advancement by Target Group

7.6 Interim Conclusion 5: Target Group and Motivators

The findings suggest that professionals in management positions within Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Core Facilities (CFs) primarily engage with the program as a means of career advancement. Their motivation is strongly linked to developing leadership and decision-making skills, aligning well with the program's objectives.

While learning new tasks remains a key motivator across all groups, established professionals in management positions are less driven by the challenge itself. Moreover, they seem to experience a stronger external expectation to participate, possibly reflecting professional norms or institutional pressures.

This indicates that the program intended audience within RI and CF management, align with its leadership-focused and structural objectives. It also highlights the importance of positioning the program as a strategic career development tool rather than solely a skills-based training opportunity.

Target Group's reasons to participate in the RltrainPlus program

- **Career advancement** – Professionals in management positions engage with the program primarily to advance their careers.
- **Development of leadership and decision-making skills** – Their motivation is closely linked to enhancing these skills, which aligns with the program's objectives.
- **External expectations** – Established professionals are more strongly influenced by external pressures or professional norms to participate, than less established individuals.

7.7 Professional Perspective

This next sector shortly represents the perspective of the professionals in the field, concerning the positioning of RIs and CFs, on work content and their coping in their everyday work life.

The participants were asked to assess the role of Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Core Facilities (CFs) in a broader context. They rated each statement on a scale from 1 to 5.

The participants appear to believe that RIs and CFs offer rather good career opportunities and that the services provided by RIs and CFs are generally both appreciated and supported by academia, with both statements averaging around 3,7. There is slightly less agreement that academia offers sufficient support to RIs, though the average still suggests a general belief that there is enough support. Overall, it seems that participants feel RIs are relatively well-positioned, but with some restraint (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Survey Data Perception of RIs and CFs

When asked about the importance of specific skills for their work, participants rated each skill on a scale from 1 (not important) to 4 (very important).

All skills were on average rated as important. The lowest-rated skill required for the participants' work was empirical work or research of any kind, followed by supporting scholars and developing research methods and technologies for support. This distribution is especially interesting when linked to the background presented above, where one-quarter of the participants indicated that they work as scientific staff in research-related tasks. This and the rather high standard deviation

for those tasks suggest that these skills are strongly dependent on the specific positions and roles within the organization. The most important skills, with a low standard deviation, were communication skills, which appear to be essential for nearly all survey participants. Additionally, there is a high demand for skills related to management and administrative tasks.

These findings align well with the program's objectives, particularly in promoting management skills and providing participants with a deeper understanding of the workings of RIs.

Task Importance

Figure 19: Survey Data Task Importance

When asked about their satisfaction concerning different aspects of their work the participants could rate each aspect on a scale from 1 not satisfied to 5 highly satisfied.

Generally speaking, the sample appears to be quite satisfied with various aspects of their work. There is higher satisfaction regarding the content of their work and the working hours, compared to slightly lower satisfaction career perspective and specifically the salary seems to be the most unsatisfactory (see Figure 20).

Participants were also asked to rate their confidence in specific skills on a scale from 1 to 6. They were asked about both general skills and work-related tasks.

The participants rated their efficacy quite high, averaging around 5 for both general tasks and work-specific tasks (see Figure 21 and

Task Efficacy

Figure 22). The participants rated their confidence while doing everyday tasks as well as communicating with coworkers the highest with an average of over 5. They also seem to be confident in their own abilities in difficult situations. The lowest ratings show up when asked about doing scientific work as well as managing a team and doing infrastructure work. While scientific work does not seem to be as relevant to most professionals, this answer distribution does not generate a concern. Compared to that, team management and infrastructure work should play a role in the target audience of the program. A lack of these skills could raise concerns. These specific skills, with low confidence levels, are emphasized by the training opportunities of the RltrainPlus program. However, if the program itself has had an impact on strengthening the confidence of the participants cannot be concluded from this cross-sectional survey, as no data on the confidence in these tasks before attending the program is available. But this shows a strong need in programs offering learning opportunities specifically focused on RI related work.

Satisfaction

Figure 20: Survey Data Satisfaction with Work Aspects

General Efficacy

Figure 21: Survey Data General Efficacy

Task Efficacy

Figure 22: Survey Data Task Efficacy

7.8 Interim Conclusion 6: Participants Needs

In summary, it can be said that participants generally have a positive view of the roles in RIs and CFs, but sometimes desire more input or cooperation with academic structures. The high ratings of the relevance of communication and management tasks highlights the need for a training offering focused on these areas. The RitrainPlus courses address both the management aspects and provide additional input to better navigate the field of RI, which could improve confidence in performing such tasks. There also seems to be a greater uncertainty regarding the self-assessment of the participants team management and infrastructure skills even after completing the program. The impact of the program on the improvement of these skills cannot be measured in this cross-sectional analysis, but it would be a valuable aspect to explore in a longitudinal approach.

Objective and Course Content of RitrainPlus program

- ▶ Course content fits the needs of the participants
- ▶ Required Skills:
 - Management
 - Communication
 - Navigating RI Work

7.9 Program and Course Evaluation

In this section we want to look at the evaluation of the program and the specific courses in the survey.

About 40 percent of the sample participated in the *'Managing the Lifestyle of an RI'* course, making it the most popular, closely followed by the *'Socio-economic Impact of RIs'* course. Around 30 percent of participants were enrolled in both *'Data Management'* and *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry'*. The least chosen courses were *'Team Building and Development'* with 15 percent participation, and *'Coaching Development Programme'*, with less than 8 percent.

Figure 23: Survey Data Course Enrolment Rate

The participants were asked about their experience with the overall course program as well as with the specific courses. When asked about the courses, two aspects focused on the content based on the program description, while one question addressed the structural aspects. The structural question was asked the same way for each course, while the content-related questions were tailored to the specific course. Each statement could be rated on a scale of 1 to 5.

The course program was rated positively, with an average score of around four for all questions. Especially the relevance of the courses was rated highly. People would rather apply to courses from a new course program than from the same course program, although opinions here seem to differ more strongly, as indicated by a comparably high standard deviation. The question regarding the fulfilment or exceeding of expectations was also rated slightly lower than other items (see Table 36: Survey Data Impression Course ProgramTable 36).

The 'Socio-Economic Impact of RIs' course also received an average rating of around four for all assessed items. This applies to both the structural aspects and the course content. In terms of content, participants rated the insight into socio-economic impacts more highly than the aspect of being taught how to communicate this knowledge to others. (see Table 37).

'*Coaching Development Programme*' was rated even higher, receiving an average score just below 5 across all three items (see Table 38). This course received overall the best scores.

'*Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications in RIs and CFs*' achieved an average rating a bit below four across all aspects (see Table 39). Although this rating is overall quite good, it is one of the lower ratings when compared to other courses. When examining the course feedback gathered after participation, as presented above, this course received the highest ratings. This indicates that the ratings should be interpreted with caution, as they only reflect specific aspects of the course feedback. In particular, the feedback presented in the previous chapter has limited validity due to the very small sample size. Additionally, the course feedback presented in the previous chapter refers only to the first round of the course program, whereas the feedback collected through the survey sampled all course participants, regardless of their time of participation.

'*Data Management*' was perceived very positively, with participants feeling that the course significantly enhanced their understanding of data management policies and the FAIR principles (see Table 40).

'*Managing the Lifecycle of an RI*' received a comparatively lower rating. In particular, the structure and assessment criteria seemed to generate lower responses (see Table 41).

'*Team Building and Development*' received ratings around 4, with particularly positive feedback on the content aspect (see Table 42).

'*Innovation, Entrepreneurship, and Engagement with Industry*' received ratings higher than four across all items (see Table 43).

This makes up for an average rating of the program of 4,1 (Std. Deviation 0,8) and an average rating of the courses of 3,9 (Std. Deviation 0,9).

Impression Course Program	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The courses offered were relevant to me.	66	4,26	0,9
The courses offered were matching or exceeding my expectations.	66	3,88	0,9
I found the quality of my courses to be good.	64	4,11	0,8
If the same course catalogue was continued to be offered: it is likely I will apply for another course from the same course catalogue.	65	3,85	1,2
If the course catalogue is updated: it is likely I will apply for new course from the different course catalogue.	66	4,15	0,9

Table 36: Survey Data Impression Course Program

Socio-economic impact of RIs	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The course provided a clear understanding of socio-economic impact assessment frameworks and methodologies.	26	4,19	0,8
The course enhanced my ability to communicate the socio-economic impact of RIs effectively to diverse stakeholders.	26	3,96	0,8
The course was well structured and the assessment criteria was clear.	26	4,15	0,8

Table 37: Survey Data Impression Socio-economic Impact of RIs

Coaching development programs	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The course effectively taught me how to design meaningful and achievable work and research objectives.	5	4,80	0,4
The course improved my ability to manage interpersonal relationships and build trust within my team.	5	4,80	0,4
The course was well structured and the assessment criteria was clear.	5	4,80	0,4

Table 38: Survey Data Impression Coaching Development programs

Ethical legal or social implications in RIs and CFs	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The course provided practical insights into managing ethical, legal, and social issues relevant to RIs and CFs.	16	3,88	0,8
The course increased my ability to apply knowledge of equity, inclusion, and privacy frameworks to enhance organizational leadership.	16	3,88	0,8
The course was well structured and the assessment criteria was clear.	16	3,88	0,7

Table 39: Survey Data Impression Ethical, legal and social Social Implications of RIs and CFs

Data management	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The course enhanced my understanding of data management policies and the application of FAIR principles.	20	4,70	0,9
The course strengthened my ability to implement effective data management practices that contribute to academic excellence and collaboration.	20	4,15	1,1
The course was well structured and the assessment criteria was clear.	20	4,40	0,7

Table 40: Survey Data Impression Data management

Managing the lifecycle of an RI	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The course provided practical guidance on managing transitions through various lifecycle stages of an RI.	26	4,00	0,9
The course improved my organizational leadership skills by preparing me to handle challenges across different operational phases of an RI.	26	3,62	1,2
The course was well structured and the assessment criteria was clear.	26	3,54	1,2

Table 41: Survey Data Impressions Managing the lifecycle of an RI

Team Building and Development	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The course provided effective tools for creating and managing cohesive and high-performing teams.	11	4,27	0,6
The course helped me develop communication skills essential for fostering collaboration and accountability within diverse teams.	11	4,27	0,6
The course was well structured and the assessment criteria was clear.	11	3,91	0,9

Table 42: Survey Data Impressions Team Building and Development

Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry	n	Average	Std.- Deviation
The course deepened my understanding of establishing productive relationships between RIs and industry.	21	4,10	0,8
The course enhanced my ability to apply innovative thinking and align organizational goals with industry partners for societal impact.	21	4,24	0,8
The course was well structured and the assessment criteria was clear.	21	4,10	1,2

Table 43: Survey Data Impression Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry

When relating this to our specific target group, we find that the ratings are linked to how well individuals fit within the program’s target audience. Participants who are more closely aligned with the target group are more likely to give higher ratings to both the program (Corr. 0.228; Sig. 0.066) and the courses (Corr. 0.226; Sig. 0.070).

This insight reinforces initial assessments that there may have been a partial mismatch between the intended target group and the actual participants. Since the program is specifically designed for a particular group—established professionals in the field of RI and CFS—it follows that individuals outside this target group may find the actual course content less aligned with their needs. This correlation reflects that observation.

Additionally, if participants were highly motivated extrinsically—meaning they were encouraged socially, professionally, or by their organization to take part in the program—they were also more likely to rate the courses higher (Corr. 0.257; Sig. 0.047).

This also aligns with initial expectations, that external pressure leads to higher ratings. Individuals with strong intrinsic motivation prioritize knowledge acquisition and are more critical when expectations are not met. However, when motivation is driven more by organizational or infrastructural needs, the focus shifts towards completing the course and obtaining the certificate. As a result, these individuals are less critical of the course elements.

Figure 24: Correlations Satisfaction with Program and Courses

Was the Target Group satisfied?

1.
 - ▶ The closer people are fitting the target group the more positive the feedback on the program
2.
 - ▶ The closer people are fitting the target group the more positive the feedback on the courses

It was also tested if there are specific variables relating to the specific courses, indicating a higher chance to enrol in a course.

'Socio-economic Impact of Ris' shows a closer connection to the target group with a correlation of 0,259 (Sig. 0,028).

Figure 25: Correlation Socio Economic Impact of Ris

'Innovation Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry' is also chosen more likely by people relating to the programs target population (Korr. 0,428, Sig. 0,000). This is also reflected in the correlation between affiliation with RIs and CFs and course participation, showing that people working in RIs and CFs are more likely to take part the 'Innovation Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry' course (Korr. 0,301, Sig. 0,016).

Figure 26: Correlations Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry

People working at a university or other institutions of higher education are more likely to participate in '*Managing the lifecycle of an RI*' (Korr. 0,214; Sig. 0,089). This indicates that individual stronger related to the academic field show a stronger interest in the general structure, the complete dynamics and underlying processes.

Figure 27: Correlation Managing the Lifecycle of an RI

Additionally, people that show a high self-efficacy, meaning they have strong trust in their own skills, concerning work specific as well as general tasks are more likely to complete more courses, either from the same course catalogue or from a different course catalog (Corr. 0,305, Sig. 0,019).

Figure 28: Correlation Enrolling in further Courses

7.10 Interim Conclusion 7: Course and Program Assessment

The highest participation rate in the survey came from the *'Managing the Lifestyle of an RI'* course, though a comparable higher number compared to the general participation rates of respondents also took *'Socio-Economic Impact of RIs'* as well as *'Managing the Lifecycle of an RI'*. The Socio-Economic Impact course attracted more participants from the social sciences, where a focus on empirical research could have motivated their survey participation. However, this assumption does not align with the sample group comparison, suggesting no clear trend linking discipline to survey participation.

'Coaching Development' received the highest ratings from survey participants in terms of both structure and content. Despite having fewer participants, the course, which offered both online and two-day in-person options, was well-received. With its specific focus on personal growth, relationship-building, and coaching techniques, the course provided clear expectations, which likely contributed to the positive feedback and satisfaction of the participants. The course's targeted approach helped ensure participants understood its content beforehand, leading to favourable evaluations.

Compared to that *'Managing the Lifecycle of an RI'* received lower ratings, especially on structure and building leadership skills. The course was only offered as an online lecture and has a more broader course content outlining.

'Socio-Economic Impact of RIs' as well as *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with the Industry'* were more likely to be chosen by people fitting the target group. Compared to the other courses *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with the Industry'* has a clear-defined and specifically outlined target group, which likely helped in effectively addressing the needs of the intended professionals. This clear demarcation of the course's audience probably made it easier for participants to understand the course's relevance to their professional context, leading to a more focused and beneficial learning experience.

Because people were happier with the program and the courses, if they fitted the target group better. Moreover, extrinsic motivation lead to a higher course evaluation.

8 Deeper Insight – Qualitative Interviews

The following section is covering the findings of three group interviews with participants of the first and second edition of the seven courses offered via RltrainPlus.

Participants shared their experiences, providing insights into their motivations, aspirations, likes, dislikes, and overall opinions. The interviews not only provide an initial understanding of the participants' individual and collective experiences with the program but also shed light on their backgrounds and professional trajectories. These insights represent a critical component of the evaluation process, as the experiences and perceptions of stakeholders are essential in evaluation research. This further helps to verify the initial indicators regarding the program's effectiveness and challenges found in the chapters above and to understand the dynamics behind them. Through that the program can be effectively tailored to meet the needs of both stakeholders in the field and professionals of research infrastructures. Therefore additionally, a typology of participants is included to better understand the diverse profiles and needs represented in the program.

8.1 Methodological Approach and Analysis

To collect initial data, qualitative group discussions were conducted. Three groups, each consisting of four participants, were interviewed based on guiding themes. The focus was on their motivations, experiences, and impressions of the RltrainPlus program.

This method of group interviews allows for deeper insights into the experiences of participants in the RltrainPlus program by leveraging group dynamics. Group interviews offer numerous advantages, including creating a natural conversational setting, fostering open exchange, and uncovering shared perspectives or divergences within the group. Particularly within a mixed-methods approach, such qualitative interviews can provide valuable insights that complement quantitative data.

The selection of the interview sample was intentional, based on theory, aiming to gain in-depth insights into the program's functioning. The interviewees do not represent all participants but rather provide additional input into the dynamics at play. In contrast, the survey was designed to cover a broader range of participants. The two data points must be interpreted in the context of their respective purpose and objectives. Differences in response patterns are therefore attributable to this distinction.

Figure 29: Interview and Analysis Process

The interviews were between 30 and 45 minutes long. The analysis is based on the transcripts of the interviews as well as additional notes made by the interviewer. For the analysis, a content-structured analysis combined with a typology formation based on Kuckartz (2012) is used.

The material is first reviewed and structured according to thematic content blocks. These blocks are aligned with the structure of the interview and are divided into categories such as motivation, aspirations, and positive and negative aspects. Based on these categories, the interviews are analysed, and key elements are filtered, leading to the formation of subcategories.

Furthermore, a typology formation is employed. This typology is primarily based on the participants' motivations and backgrounds and aims to provide a clearer understanding of their experiences with the RltrainPlus program.

The first part of the interview explored the reasons, motivations, and underlying circumstances for participating in the program. This was followed by a discussion on the format and organization of the courses. In the final section, the discussion centred on participants' positive and negative experiences as well as their overall assessments of the program.

Section	Intent of the Section	Question	Subquestion [Basic Information]
1	Find out who the participants are and where they come from. The main question provides a background for understanding other data points coming up in the interview	Can you tell me a bit about yourself, and how you came to work or be affiliated with research infrastructure?	(a) academic [research] post or non-academic [non research support] post? (b) attitude towards Research Infrastructure in general? (c) Feels well prepared for current tasks in RI?
2	This section mostly deals with the motives that can be named for why one joins the programme.	What motivated you to participate in the RltrainPlus program?	(a) Where did they learn from RltrainPlus? (b) Are there specific reasons they joined RltrainPlus and not other offerings?
3	How were courses and topics selected? What reasons are provided for the selection process and what was this mostly an individual or organisational guidance?	How did you choose the courses you wanted enrolled in?	(a) Were there any specific skills or knowledge areas they wanted to improve? (b) Did they consult anyone (e.g., mentors, colleagues) when deciding? (c) Was the course structure [online / onsite] or content a deciding factor? (d) Did they get all your desired courses?
4	How did the participants experience the program? Which aspects were highlighted positively, and which were criticized?	What was your experience with the program so far?	(a) What aspects of the training have been most valuable? (b) Have you encountered any challenges in completing your courses? (c) Were the courses aligned with your initial expectations?
5	What were the experiences concerning the course program and the specific courses?	How would YOU evaluate the courses you've completed or participated in?	(d) What specific elements of the courses stood out to you (positively or negatively)? (e) Was the format (e.g., online, in-person, hybrid) effective for your learning? (f) Are there any areas where you think the courses could

Section	Intent of the Section	Question	Subquestion [Basic Information]
			be improved?
6	What impact does the program have on participants' professional development? Are there any additional needs that should be addressed? This section also provides an opportunity for participants to give open feedback for the further development of the program.	What are your expectations for the program going forward?	(a) Are there additional topics or training formats you would like to see? (b) How do you think this training will impact your future work in research infrastructure?
7	This final section provides an opportunity for participants to share any additional comments in case any topics were overlooked.	Closing Questions	(a) Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience with the RI:train+ program? (b) Are there any areas we didn't cover that you think are important?

8.2.1 Background to the Interviews

All the interviews were conducted in Milano during the in-person meeting of the second edition of the RltrainPlus courses in the form of 3 group interviews ranging from 30 to 45 minutes. The specific format of a group interview was chosen to allow for a more condensed data collection, but still have a formal structure, where every participant had to provide some information on a given set of questions, however because of the free form answers possible it was possible for the interviewer to mix-up and switch or rephrase questions.

The data collection process in this part of the evaluation study was not intended to be a group discussion among the participants but a semi-structured group interview where every one of the participants had to answer a set of questions [see section before].

Concerning participants' demographic make-up, this part of the evaluation study follows the concept of a consciously selected, diversified sample structure, to provoke dialogue among the participants. Overall, 12 Participants were involved in the interviews. All interviews were made up of groups of four. The participants were selected by the interviewer beforehand based on their seniority, gender and type research infrastructure they worked for to create a maximum heterogeneity approach. The information on the participants was gained by the interviewer

during round table discussions on the day before the interviews took place. Participation was voluntary and the participants had to sign an informed consent sheet.

Of the twelve interviewees, eight were female and four were male, resulting in a stronger emphasis on women, but aligning well with the participant quotas. The participants had diverse professional backgrounds, ranging from highly experienced individuals whose primary focus is on administrative, training, or management tasks, to those aspiring to transition into management roles. Their academic backgrounds varied, with some possessing strong scientific expertise, while others had limited scientific experience. The participants were employed across a range of organizational structures, from small, local infrastructure institutions to well-established research infrastructure landmarks. Some participants had already completed their professional careers and were no longer directly involved in their previous roles but remained connected to the field. They participated in the course to contribute to others and continue their personal development.

The setting was an informal one, with comfortable couches arranged around a table, where the recording device was positioned, and the interviewer saw all the participants. The main idea was to provide some stimulus and let interviewees answer individual questions, with the interviewer guiding the flow of the talks between individuals and allowing them to exchange ideas. However, discussions were mostly cut off, as the idea was to have a group interview and not a group discussion.

Compared to individual interviews, group interviews allow for more spontaneous, emotionally direct, and authentic responses to questions. Participants may reflect on their own opinions or delve deeper in response to others' thoughts. Moreover, a relaxed, interactive, and supportive group setting can facilitate discussions on sensitive topics. Additionally, non-verbal cues can be picked up by the moderator and used to further contextualize the statements made. Possible challenges with this form of interviewing include the moderator's role. They must ensure a balanced conversation, where every participant has the opportunity to speak. Furthermore, the group dynamic must be considered during analysis, particularly with regard to interaction effects (Flick 2018).

8.2.2 Data Analysis

All data were recorded on the interviewer's device for subsequent transcription and analysis. The transcription process was carried out in two steps. Initially, a rough draft was generated using *Atrain*, a locally hosted transcription program developed by the University of Graz (Haber et al.

2024). The transcription parameters were set to accommodate group interviews conducted in English, involving five speakers.

These preliminary transcriptions provided an initial overview of the material and facilitated a better understanding of the field notes taken by the interviewer. Subsequently, the transcripts were manually reviewed and corrected by a second researcher to ensure accuracy.

Simultaneously, the interviewer began a preliminary analysis and developed an initial typology, the second researcher created key descriptions of the findings based on coding of the transcripts and compared the findings with the first research initial analysis and typology of the material. This phase culminated in a collaborative dialogue between the interviewer and the second researcher, during which the typology and key aspects of the results were discussed and refined. The overall process of synthesizing the data and creating the typology was guided by qualitative data analysis frameworks established by Mayring and Kuckartz. The first phase, following Philipp Mayring's approach (1994), involved paraphrasing individual statements and synthesizing them into key arguments. The second phase, typology development, adhered to Udo Kuckartz's methodology (2012).

These steps were taken as Philipp Mayring's qualitative content analysis is a systematic approach to analysing textual data - like the interview data created during the evaluation - , emphasizing the structuring and synthesis of information. This approach allows to break down interview data into manageable units, paraphrasing statements of the participants to capture their essence, and categorizing them based on thematic relevance. This structured approach allowed the researchers to distil the complex qualitative information on the impression the participants had from RltrainPlus into the key arguments we will present in the next section, while maintaining the context and meaning of their original responses.

By focusing on step-by-step analysis, the Mayring inspired approach ensures transparency and replicability, making his methodology particularly suited for the interpretive part of the evaluation study.

This provides examples of how the interviews were filtered and categorized:

<p>“ of course it can be also experience around the course, like <i>social experience, social connection</i>, first of all “</p>	<p>Social Connections through program</p>	
<p>“every time when I'm participating in different kinds of activities like this, when I'm speaking with people or networking, I can find different information about this.”</p>	<p>Exchange of information</p>	
<p>“I like that I get different perspective because there are different domain and I like it because usually when you focus, when you are in a group you work in that domain and you know which are, for example the choices that we made in that domain, but this doesn't mean that are the only one so it's like, an <i>open-minded force</i>.”</p>	<p>Different perspective and new input through connection and exchange</p>	<p>Social Connection and exchange with the other participants are important aspects of the experience in the program</p>
<p>“now I see that some other people have the same questions and so it enables discussion and also will be having more skills to face these questions”</p>	<p>Relating to people and their problems concerning work</p>	

For the second part of the analysis Udo Kuckartz's framework for qualitative analysis was used, as it focuses on creating typologies to organize and interpret data systematically. With this approach, the researches could identify recurring patterns, themes, or characteristics within the data gained during the group interviews, creating the chance to formulate typologies - however the decision was made to treat types not as exclusionary and allow for individual cases to feed into several theory-generating types. As the data analysis methodology from Kuckartz emphasizes the iterative process of coding, categorization, and refinement, it was necessary to involve the two researchers not only for validation as during the first coding steps, but also during the whole data analysis process, allowing for more detailed insights into broader classifications. After an initial categorization and sorting by the interviewer based on the gathered material and impressions from the interviews, the second researcher reviewed the material and verified the systematization to ensure it aligned with their own observations.

The initial categorization was strongly guided by the interview framework, as the predefined themes and questions shaped the first structuring of the data. At the same time, an inductive approach was applied to assess whether these predefined categories adequately captured the themes emphasized by the interviewees themselves. This allowed for a dynamic comparison between the theoretical structure of the interview guide and the actual focal points that emerged from the discussions. As a result, adjustments were made where necessary to integrate participant-driven themes, ensuring that the categorization remained both systematic and reflective of the data.

In the subsequent phases, a continuous, iterative process of refinement led to minor adjustments in the categorization, formed through the exchange between the two researchers. Through this, the data was further analysed and contextualized to ensure coherence and validity.

After the initial categorization, the interview data was revisited multiple times to maintain consistency and accuracy. Each review allowed for small but meaningful adjustments in both the typology and the categories, ensuring that the framework fully captured the nuances within the data while remaining aligned with the theoretical foundation.

As the analysis progressed, additional subcategories were introduced inductively to account for less obvious patterns or emerging themes. These refinements enabled a more detailed differentiation within the main categories, allowing for a more precise interpretation of participant responses. Furthermore, socio-demographic variables, such as age and professional background, were integrated into the analysis to explore how individual characteristics influenced participants' perspectives. This process resulted in the development of a typology that categorized the participants based on recurring patterns and key themes identified in the analysis.

The final categorization system was developed through the integration of both deductively established proto-categories and inductively emerging insights. By continuously comparing the initial, framework-based categorization with the themes that participants emphasized in their responses, the researchers ensured that the typology was both theoretically grounded and empirically supported. The resulting typology was then critically examined in relation to other data sources to confirm its representativeness within the broader theoretical framework.

Ultimately, this rigorous process led to the creation of a coherent and systematic interpretative framework that effectively captured the diversity of perspectives within the dataset while maintaining methodological transparency and reliability.

8.3 Results – Insights into the qualitative study

The results are divided into two parts. The first part closely follows the interview guide and the themes identified from the data. It focuses on the experiences and impressions of the participants. The second part focuses on the typology derived from the respondents' answers and presents the four different typologies of RltrainPlus participants along with their characteristics.

8.3.1 Key Findings based on the core questions of the interview guide

In this section, the major results and implications from the analysis of the group discussions are presented, providing a detailed overview of the participants' motivations, aspirations, and feedback regarding the RltrainPlus program. These findings offer concrete insights into the aspects of the program that participants found beneficial, as well as the specific challenges they encountered, helping to highlight areas for improvement in future iterations of the program.

8.3.1.1 MOTIVATIONS

A significant part of the areas of interest in the interviews was to explore participants' motivations for attending the program. The aim was to identify the underlying factors—both personal and structural drivers—that influence individuals to engage in such programs, as well as specifically, their decision to join this particular program.

Participants joined the RltrainPlus program for diverse reasons, spanning professional growth, organizational needs, and personal development. The program and courses were chosen not only for their content and field-specific focus but also for their accessibility and the ease with which they could be integrated into the participants' professional schedules. Following main motivators can be highlighted:

Career Advancement and Upskilling

Many participants sought the program as an opportunity to enhance their careers and acquire new skills. The aspect of “lifelong learning” emerged as a shared value, with participants emphasizing the importance of staying updated and informed in their areas of expertise. Those at the earlier stages of their careers viewed the program as a means to gain the expertise needed for advancing into management roles.

“I attended these courses because, for me, it's very important to consolidate lifelong training and upskilling. I wanted to stay updated on topics like data and research management.”

Referring back to the quantitative data, we can see that established professionals focus on developing leadership skills and advancing their careers, whereas individuals outside of RI and CFS expect to attain management positions. This suggests that career advancement and upskilling serve as key motivators at different stages of the career path, though with distinct focal points.

Bridging Knowledge Gaps in Specialized Areas

The program's specific focus on Research Infrastructures (RIs) attracted participants seeking a deeper understanding of the field's connections and dynamics. The courses offered valuable insights into the interconnected and transnational nature of RIs, helping participants bridge specific knowledge gaps in this specialized domain.

“It was an opportunity for me to explore the overall landscape of research infrastructures, especially since my manager encouraged me to participate.”

This particularly highlights the complexity of the field and the lack of a specialized training program for professionals in this area. Individuals work at specific intersections of the processes but must also understand other dynamics to grasp the full complexity of these processes. Targeted programs are needed to address these knowledge gaps by offering courses on these topics

Accessibility and Affordability

The program's accessibility and affordability were also significant factors. Participants noted the limited availability of other programs specifically tailored to RIs, making RltrainPlus a unique option. The program's cost-effectiveness and flexible structure further facilitated participation, enabling individuals to integrate it into their schedules and budgets effectively.

“The free aspect of the program was a major factor—most similar opportunities are cost-prohibitive.”

Most participants joined the program out of self-motivation. However, some were made aware of the program by colleagues or encouraged to participate by their supervisors. Motivation to participate was therefore influenced not only by personal drive but also by the informational networks participants were part of. The encouragement from colleagues or supervisors often played a role, as did simply becoming aware of such programs in the first place.

8.3.1.2 ASPIRATIONS

In addition to exploring motivation, the interest also lies in understanding how participants intend to use the knowledge and insights gained from the courses, and what objectives they aim to pursue through this implementation.

Participants aspired to apply the knowledge gained in their professional contexts, share insights with colleagues, and fill specific knowledge gaps. The following key themes, building upon each other, were identified:

Dissemination of knowledge

With the knowledge and specific insights gained from the program, participants plan to apply their expertise within their organizations. They aim to support their colleagues by sharing these insights, offering specialized expertise, training and mentoring fellow researchers.

“For me, this was about gaining expertise to train young researchers in socioeconomic evaluation—a topic that’s often neglected.”

Building capacity

Expanding on this they aspire to build capacity in their organizations, particularly in highly specialized and not widely addressed areas such as data management and socioeconomic impact. These topics are often underrepresented and require niche expertise, which participants aim to develop further. By doing so, they hope to fill critical knowledge gaps and provide valuable support to their organizations.

“I wanted to develop my understanding of innovation and industry partnerships to better support my organization’s goals.”

Expanding horizons

Several participants highlighted the complexity and interconnectedness of Research Infrastructures RIs. They intend to leverage the insights gained during the courses to more effectively address both organizational and societal challenges through a better understanding of the complexity.

“My aspiration was to bring the knowledge back to Israel and adapt it to local research contexts, so the program was a key opportunity for that.”

8.3.1.3 LIKES AND DISLIKES OF THE PROGRAM AND ITS STRUCTURE

The participants were also asked to share their experiences with the RitrainPlus program. As positive aspects the program's flexibility, as well as the networking opportunities and quality of instruction were consistently praised. Participants highlighted challenges related to the program's intensity, communication, and session structure.

Organisational Aspects

The program's accessibility, already highlighted as a major motivator, was viewed very positively. In particular, the availability of online courses allowed participants, who are mostly fully integrated into their daily work routines, to combine their professional responsibilities with professional development. This is especially relevant since the program attracted participants from different geographical locations, making participation possible for some in the first place.

“The online format made it easy to balance work and training, and the recorded materials were invaluable for review.”

However, limited information provided beforehand, particularly regarding scheduling, but also concerning the content and requirements of the courses, sometimes made organization challenging.

“The courses were so dense that I often had to revisit the materials to fully absorb everything. Clearer communication about the workload would have helped.”

One group reported technical issues, which can occasionally arise during online sessions. Additionally, some lectures exceeded their allotted time, leading to scheduling overlaps. At times, insufficient breaks during online sessions impacted participants' ability to maintain focus.

“The lack of breaks during long online sessions made it difficult to stay focused and engaged.”

Content-related aspects

The participants praised the content of the courses, particularly appreciating the field-specific topics as well as the broader perspective they provided, which helped to enlarge their horizons, introduce new aspects, and offer a clearer view of the bigger picture. This seems to align with the findings of previous chapters, where the course content were generally rated quite high. However, many found the courses quite demanding, especially given the varied backgrounds of participants and the range of professional experience among them. Some prior knowledge was assumed, which increased the workload for those who lacked the necessary foundations.

“Some sessions assumed prior expertise, which made it harder for beginners like me to follow along.”

Despite this, participants were impressed with the lecturers, who were highly qualified in their respective fields and provided a practical, hands-on approach to the courses. The accessibility and support provided by the lecturers were also highlighted and greatly appreciated.

“The trainers were very supportive and approachable, which made the learning process engaging and impactful.”

Furthermore, the materials provided were greatly appreciated and considered highly useful. Participants expressed their intention to continue using these resources in their work and professional development moving forward.

Moreover, the networking opportunities provided by the courses were highlighted by several participants and represented an important aspect of their course experience. These opportunities enabled knowledge sharing, collaboration, and discussions of common challenges with others facing similar issues. In particular, the exchange with individuals from diverse areas and disciplines offered valuable insights by bringing different perspectives to shared issues and topics.

“I valued the diversity of perspectives during group discussions—it really broadened my understanding.”

The main **positive aspects** highlighted were:

- Online accessibility
- Networking opportunities
- Practical content and experienced trainers

The main **negative aspects** raised were:

- High workload and assumed prior knowledge
- Demanding sessions

In summary, most of the issues raised pertained to the organization and structure of the program. In terms of content and opportunities, participants were highly satisfied and praised the program's offerings and inputs.

What positive and negative Aspects were highlighted?

- + Online accessibility
- + Networking opportunities
- + Practical content and experienced trainers
- High workload and assumed prior knowledge
- Demanding sessions

8.3.1.4 OVERALL OPINIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Participants were overwhelmingly positive about the program's value, particularly its social and networking benefits. However, they suggested several structural improvements to address organizational hurdles. These included reducing repeated content across different courses, providing clearer instructions, and enhancing the overall structure for better cohesion.

The program was a great opportunity to upskill and enhance my knowledge of research infrastructures—it exceeded my expectations.”

Participants also expressed a desire for hybrid models that combine the flexibility of online learning with the benefits of in-person networking opportunities.

“Hybrid models with in-person networking sessions would add tremendous value to the overall learning experience.”

Tailoring course difficulty levels to accommodate varying levels of prior knowledge and professional experience was another commonly suggested improvement, to help accommodate participants from different backgrounds and expertise. Especially the wish for foundational courses that could serve as a baseline for the more advanced, specialized courses was voiced.

Additionally, more comprehensive pre-course communication regarding scheduling, workload, and prerequisites was identified as a key area for enhancement. Providing more detailed information about the course content, expectations, associated workload, and specific requirements would help potential participants make more informed decisions and better assess whether the program aligns with their needs and capabilities. Additionally, timely communication about dates, deadlines, and other key details would greatly assist working professionals in planning and managing their schedules effectively.

In summary, the main areas identified for improvement suggested by the participants include

- introducing hybrid models
- tailoring course difficulty levels
- and prioritizing improved pre-course communication.

Overall, however, the program was very well received in terms of its relevance and usefulness. Participants expressed general satisfaction with the program, found the experience positive, and considered the content highly beneficial.

“Despite the challenges, I’d recommend the program because it provided tools I could immediately apply in my job.”

8.4 Interim Conclusion 8: Content and General Conditions

The group interviews showed that the content was generally well received, which aligns with the feedback from the course evaluations presented in the second part of the empirical results. Participants of the program seem to recognize the relevance of the topics presented and appreciate the practical approach, which helps relate the learned content to their field of work. However, there seems to be a suggestion for more basic courses to help build a foundation for individuals who lack a certain background. This indicates a mismatch between the program's initial goal of further training professionals already working in the field and enhancing their skills. The RltrainPlus program was tailored to meet the needs of established professionals working in the fields of RI and CFs. Basic courses would not align with the original objectives of the program. However, based on the out-of-target-group participants identified in the previous chapters, as well as the needs expressed in the interviews, it becomes quite clear that there is a strong demand for more foundational courses.

That being said, participants also struggled with the organizational aspects of the program. Especially for those already working in the field, additional training should be compatible with their work routines. Better communication prior to the start of the program and more detailed information on both organizational and content-related aspects are crucial to ensure that courses can be selected and completed efficiently.

Moreover, another important aspect for the participants, besides developing specific skills, was the opportunity for connection and exchange within the courses. The chance to engage with others in the field and receive interdisciplinary input seems to be highly valued. This also reflects the foundation of RI and CFs, which focus on better accessibility, interdisciplinary collaboration, and exchange.

While the survey primarily focused on content-based feedback, the interviews provided a more nuanced perspective on the program. While course content appears to be a key factor in choosing the program, other aspects – like the exchange or organisational issues - are highly significant for the overall training experience.

Moreover, the interviews highlighted additional unmet needs. As discussed in previous chapters, a substantial portion of participants did not fully align with the intended target group. The interviews revealed that for these individuals—typically less advanced or established professionals, possibly at the beginning of their careers in RI and CFs—there remains a strong interest in learning. However, they require a different approach and alternative offerings compared to the program's original design.

8.5 Participant Typology

The RitrainPlus program successfully addressed a range of participant needs, from professional development to organizational capacity building. While the program's strengths lie in its content, flexibility, and practical relevance, the feedback suggests opportunities to enhance its delivery and accessibility.

Participants' professional backgrounds play a significant role in shaping their motivations and needs. The diverse backgrounds of participants reflect varied goals and expectations, offering valuable insights for refining future iterations of the program. Typologies can assist in identifying specific needs and determining what adjustments are required. They help to understand which aspects of the program benefit different participants and where particular challenges arise for specific groups.

Based on the interviews, the 12 participants can be categorized into the following types:

(The typologies are not mutually exclusive. Multiple typologies can apply to a single participant and can overlap or interact in meaningful ways.)

The Lifelong Learners

These participants are driven by a strong sense of personal development and a commitment to lifelong learning. They often are already well-established in their chosen career paths and do not have an explicit need for further training related to their current job roles. Their motivation is deeply intrinsic, stemming from a desire to grow personally rather than from external requirements.

“I believe in lifelong training. These courses were a perfect fit for my personal and professional growth.”

As a result, they often enroll in multiple courses, selecting topics that are diverse and broadly spread rather than narrowly focused. The choice of subjects is frequently guided by personal interest rather than immediate professional relevance. This reflects their exploratory approach to learning, prioritizing curiosity and self-enrichment over direct applicability to their career. They are interested in exploring diverse perspectives and overarching frameworks, as well as delving into specific topics. Lifelong learners have already participated in multiple training programs and possess the capability to secure funding within their organizations or other available means.

The Career Advancers

These participants are primarily focused on leveraging the program to enhance their career prospects and gain recognition within their fields. They are often in the early to mid-stages of their professional journey, seeking to establish a stronger foundation for advancement or to shift focus and responsibilities within their field. Some are transitioning into management or more leadership-oriented roles. They aim to deepen their understanding of the interrelations and overarching structures of research infrastructure. This broader perspective enables them to tackle topics more comprehensively, situate their work within a larger context, and enhance their expertise in specific areas. In some cases, they are strongly encouraged or at least supported by their superiors to participate in training opportunities.

“I took these courses to move into science diplomacy and funding—it’s a critical step in my career progression.”

In addition, they are motivated to acquire new skills that are specifically relevant to their goals within their field and beneficial for advancing into targeted positions. These skills support their ambitions to take on greater responsibilities, such as management roles, and allow them to perform these roles more effectively and with a well-rounded perspective. Therefore, they seek targeted knowledge and select their courses specifically to address these needs.

“I suppose that we invest also personally on training. So the importance is that training is not more general, but focused on our expertise, role.”

For Career Advancers, it is particularly important that the course and its program have practical applications. They highly value hands-on approaches in their training and are looking for skills that can be transferred to their everyday work.

The Knowledge Disseminators

These participants are driven by a strong desire to learn and share their knowledge within their organizations or professional networks, including mentoring younger researchers and supporting peers. Often in established managerial or senior roles, they have a solid foundation in their careers but are eager to further their education, gain more specialized knowledge, and deepen their expertise. They view these opportunities as crucial for broadening their horizons and gaining a deeper understanding of the dynamics and diverse perspectives within their field.

They appear to feel a strong sense of responsibility towards both their organization and their role within the field, striving to contribute meaningfully and assist others. Committed to applying what they learn in practice, they aim to pass on their insights to colleagues, ensuring a positive impact through spreading expertise within their organization and across the broader professional community.

"I participated to transfer my knowledge to colleagues and promote similar training events."

The Systemic Improvers

These participants are motivated by a desire for improvement, aiming to address gaps or inefficiencies within their organisations or research infrastructure systems. With a practical focus, they are interested in acquiring tools and frameworks that can enhance organisational practices. Their goal is to take the knowledge they gain and apply it within their organisation or in the institutions and organisations across their country.

They are also highly interested in multiple perspectives and value the exchange and networking opportunities to discuss problems from different viewpoints and backgrounds. This exchange of ideas is essential for them to gain deeper insights and apply innovative solutions to improve their professional environments.

"I wanted to learn about data management to establish better practices in our research projects."

8.6 Interim Conclusion 9: Target Group and Expectation

When looking at the typology, it becomes clear that regarding the structure, there was no significant difference in assessment across the participant types. Participants from all types experienced difficulties with the unclear structure and informational gaps. The differences emerge primarily in relation to the content. Career Advancers and Systemic Improvers express a need for more practical focus. They specifically request courses that address organizational structures and management issues. Furthermore, some participants find the courses rather demanding and would appreciate a more substantially accessible approach, offering courses in basic concepts and gradually advancing to more specific topics. A big importance for them, is the application-oriented aspect. They want to be able to directly apply what they learn in their professional environments.

In contrast, Lifelong Learners are more open to a broader range of topics. They are interested in both specific and general subjects, and seem to be more flexible in their expectations regarding the program's content.

Nevertheless, it is important to note that all participant types share a strong intrinsic motivation to learn. The desire to acquire new knowledge is a key factor for all, even if other considerations, such as career progression or organizational roles, also influence their engagement with the program.

In contrast to the survey, the interviews revealed more critical feedback. While the survey responses regarding specific courses and the program in general were generally positive with only slight variations, the interviews highlighted concerns and issues more clearly. This difference is partly due to the sampling method and the contrasting data collection formats. The surveys provide a structured framework for evaluation and offer insights into the overall reception of the program, while the interviews, being more open-ended, allow for a deeper exploration of specific problems, enhanced by probing questions, open responses, and group dynamics. The negative aspects raised in the interviews do not imply that the program was poorly received, but rather highlight areas with potential for improvement and further development and suggest opportunities for refining the program.

9 Overview and Summary of Main Results

9.1 Descriptive Distribution Inequalities

The evaluation results reveal certain imbalances in the distribution of participants across different groups. Notably, the program attracted a significantly higher number of women. This is further emphasised in courses related to interpersonal skills, ethics, and organizational development, such as *'Coaching Development Programme, Ethical, Legal and Social Implications in Ris And Cfs'*, *'Managing The Lifecycle of an RI'*, and *'Team Building and Development'*. The *'Data Management'* course, however, saw a higher proportion of men. Additionally, the majority of participants come from the natural sciences and medicine, while fewer participants are from the social sciences, humanities, or technical studies. Only *'Socio-economic Impact of Ris'* managed to attract more participants from the field of social science and humanities.

9.2 Target Group Alignment

The program seems to have successfully reached its intended target group—professionals in research infrastructure (RI) and core facilities (CFs)—but with some discrepancies. While about two-thirds of the participants work in research infrastructure, a considerable portion is from scientific or technical roles rather than administrative positions. Notably, the interviews revealed that some participants were at the early stages of their careers, indicating that the program also attracted individuals who are not yet in established management roles. While the program was tailored for individuals in leadership positions or individuals who are on the verge of taking this career step, a demand was noted from those outside of these positions who sought knowledge regarding the operations of RIs and CFs, revealing a gap between the program's original target and the broader needs within the field.

9.3 Assessment of Courses Offerings

There are noticeable differences between the courses in terms of participant composition, content, and alignment with the target group. Courses such as *'Coaching Development Programme'* and *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry'* effectively reached well-established professionals in management roles, while *'Data Management'* appealed more to technicians. The *'Innovation, Entrepreneurship And Engagement With Industry'* course attracted many from the medical and health sciences fields, while *'Socio-economic Impact of RIs'* saw a higher participation from the social sciences. The content in these courses was

largely well-received, particularly the '*Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Engagement with Industry*' course, which showed a strong alignment with the expectations of the participants and is more popular with the programs target group. Additionally, the correlation analysis generally show that the assessment of the program and courses is positively influenced by the alignment of the persons background with the target group.

Furthermore, if people strongly believe in their own skills, it is more likely they will go on and take further courses with the program.

9.4 Content Satisfaction

The course feedback, the survey, as well as the interviews, show that participants were generally satisfied with the content offered by the courses. The majority of participants appreciated the practical, hands-on approach of the courses, which helped them relate the learned content to their professional roles. Additionally, the quality of trainers and the networking opportunities within the courses were highlighted as key positive aspects. Participants particularly valued the emphasis on leadership, innovation, and management skills, which align well with their professional development needs. The practical applicability of the content to real-world situations within research infrastructures and core facilities was also widely appreciated.

9.5 Challenges and Issues

Despite the positive reception of the program's content, several challenges emerged, particularly related to the organizational aspects. Participants expressed concerns regarding the unclear structure and informational gaps. The program's intensive workload and the assumption of prior knowledge were cited as barriers. Many also found the program demanding and would appreciate a more accessible, step-by-step approach, especially in terms of foundational topics. Additionally, the participants emphasized the importance of better communication prior to the program's start and more detailed information on both organizational and content-related aspects to ensure smoother course selection and completion.

10 Contextualization of the Results

The last section focuses on the contextualization and connection of all the major findings regarding the target group, content, as well as the dynamics and interactions between them. It aims to provide a holistic overview of the evaluation and insights from all data points. While the administrative data serves as the foundation for understanding the group reached, the course assessment provides an outlook on potential limitations, and the survey and interviews delve deeper, expanding the understanding of the actual impacts and manifestations of the program in practice.

It is important to note that the data sources offer different access points to the research object, and within their respective frameworks, the insights support different aspects. While the survey is based on a full collection of responses from the participants, the participants had the option to freely choose whether or not to take part in the survey. This introduces a non-response bias, which may be reflected in the results. Therefore, referring to the applicant data is crucial in order to clarify the extent and nature of any bias present.

On the other hand, the interviewees were specifically selected by the researchers. Here, the focus was not on the representativeness of the participant group, but on covering a range of different backgrounds in order to gain deeper insights into the various manifestations of the program, depending on the individuals' backgrounds. A selection bias arises in this case, as the selection took place during an on-site event of the program in Milan. Not all participants were present at this time. However, the selection followed very specific criteria, which allowed for insights into the perspectives of the different individuals involved.

Through this connection, the results of the evaluation, based on the goals outlined at the beginning, are presented. We identified who signed up and participated in the program, how the courses and programs were received, and provided insights into specific motivations, perspectives, and engagement with the program. Based on this, recommendations or actions for improving the program are proposed, specifically aimed at better aligning the interactions and interests between the program, the field, and the participants.

Based on the findings from the all the different parts of the evaluation, it is evident that the RltrainPlus program has generally been well-received. This is reflected in the survey as well as in the interviews with generally very positive feedback on various aspects. Most participants want to use the program to advance their career and have a strong intrinsic motivation to take part in the program, as the survey showed. However, participants' diverse professional backgrounds and needs have led to targeted expectations and various needs from the course offerings. While the

program successfully reaches many professionals already established in research infrastructures (RIs) and core facilities (CFs), a substantial number of participants also seems to fall out of the initial targeted group.

The application data indicates that 50 percent of participants are not primarily employed in administrative roles. However, survey results suggest that while their main professional focus may not be administrative, many still engage in administrative tasks. These discrepancies can be attributed to both selection bias and operationalization errors. Whereas the classification in the application data relies solely on job titles, the survey explicitly asked participants about their primary roles within the RI or CF, as well as any team leadership duties they may hold. While the categorization of roles also suggests that only approximately 50 percent of participants are primarily work in management or administrative tasks, around two-thirds still hold management responsibilities. Nevertheless, there still appears to be a considerable number of participants without leadership or decision-making responsibilities, indicating a substantial group lacking experience in this area. Furthermore, the survey results indicate that 15 percent of respondents have no connection to Research Infrastructures (RIs) or Core Facilities (CFs). This group appears even larger in the application data, with around 20 percent of participants working outside of RIs or CFs. This data highlights a clear issue regarding the professional backgrounds of the participants compared to the intended target group for the program. There is a discrepancy between the participants' actual roles and the profile of professionals the program aims to address, suggesting that a portion of the participants may not fully benefit from the course content, as their roles may not align with the program's focus on research infrastructure management and related administrative responsibilities. The interviews provide additional confirmation regarding this issue, as it becomes clear that many of the concerns raised are linked to a mismatch between the participants' backgrounds and the initial program objectives.

Concerning the courses content, on the one hand, there is a clear demand for advanced courses that allow established professionals to deepen their expertise, refine their skills, and gain new perspectives on the management and operation of RIs and CFs. The interviews show that these participants seek specialized content that supports their professional growth and helps them tackle complex organizational challenges. The RitrainPlus program's offerings can effectively address these needs. The exiting course content seems to be rated quite positively by this target group.

However, what should be noted is that participants might still be in the process of transitioning into management positions or are just beginning a transition into the Field of RIs. These participants mostly fall under the category of "Career Advancers." While they typically already

have some experience in the field and a basic understanding of Research Infrastructure (RI) structures, a lack of specific management experience may still be present. As a result, they seek courses tailored to developing the necessary skills for advancing in their careers. For these individuals, courses specifically focused on management skills can be highly beneficial.

Survey results also show that most participants did not take the full range of courses but instead selected one or two out of the program, indicating a very intentional approach, choosing specific ones tailored to their career development. This suggests that many individuals approach the program with a clear focus on acquiring targeted skills to advance their professional trajectories. However, the interviews paint a slightly different picture, as many of the respondents reported taking multiple courses. This discrepancy could stem from selection bias, as the participants in the interviews were likely particularly motivated and engaged individuals who took greater advantage of the program's offerings.

The survey data indicates that participants exhibit the lowest levels of self-efficacy in leadership skills and RI-specific tasks (besides scientific tasks). On the one hand, this highlights the relevance of the program in addressing these skill gaps. On the other hand, it suggests a need to adapt the program to different proficiency levels, ensuring that participants with varying degrees of prior knowledge and experience receive the appropriate support to develop their competencies effectively. It is important to note that while these values are the lowest relative to the other items, they are not low in absolute terms, and there are no extreme disparities in the responses.

On the other hand, a key observation is the presence of participants who are just beginning their involvement with RIs and CFs or are engaged in research or technical roles without administrative responsibilities. Additionally, a notable portion of participants does not directly work within RIs or CFs, which might explain a lack of familiarity with the structural and operational dynamics that the courses assume as a foundation. For these individuals the course content can be difficult to follow, resulting in an increased workload and difficulty engaging fully with the material.

There appears to be significant interest within the field in professional development and the acquisition of specific skills, even at early career stages. To address this, a more broadly structured course offering could be beneficial. A concept involving sequential or tiered courses may prove useful, ensuring that courses are aligned with one another and tailored to participants' current knowledge levels. It would be important for the courses to meet individuals where they are in their professional and skill development.

Additionally, clearer communication is needed regarding the expected baseline knowledge and the intended audience for each course or course module. While target groups have been defined for the courses, they are often described in relatively broad terms, providing little guidance for

potential participants on whether a course aligns with their specific role and expertise. More precise delineations are required to effectively reach the desired target groups. This would also help prevent individuals who have no connection to the field from enrolling in the program.

Furthermore, a clear description of course expectations, prerequisites, and workload distribution could help ensure better alignment between participants' backgrounds and course content, preventing potential mismatches and providing applicants with sufficient insight to determine which courses are suitable and feasible for them.

This issue must also be considered in the broader context of available training opportunities. While there appear to be networking organizations, supporting bodies, and auxiliary services available, a noticeable gap exists in certified training programs specifically tailored to the unique challenges of working in research infrastructures. Most offerings focus on general workshops, advanced training and education within specific disciplines, while the structural and managerial aspects crucial to operating research infrastructures are often overlooked. Some participants seem to have already maximized the available resources, highlighting the limited scope of current programs. This lack of comprehensive options makes it difficult for a single training program to address the diverse needs of individuals working in this field effectively. Especially individuals transitioning from academic roles into research infrastructure often require specific courses tailored to help them understand the structure, complexities and responsibilities of working in research infrastructure and core facilities.

This suggests that while there is a strong demand for specialized, high-level courses that address the complexities of research infrastructure management, there is also a need for more foundational training that helps individuals transition into these roles effectively.

Furthermore, the program predominantly attracts participants from the natural sciences (and health sciences), while professionals from disciplines such as the social sciences and humanities are underrepresented. In the natural sciences, as well as in medicine and health sciences, there is a notably higher proportion of professionals holding advanced degrees. This further exacerbates existing imbalances, particularly concerning the program's target group. This may reflect broader structural imbalances in the development of research infrastructures across different fields, as seen in frameworks like the ESFRI Roadmap. The particularly low participation rate from these disciplines is notable, given RltrainPlus's goal of inclusivity. Targeted outreach efforts could help engage individuals from underrepresented fields. Additionally, a review of the course program should be conducted to assess whether the course content sufficiently addresses the needs of all disciplines.

RltrainPlus also appears to be a particularly attractive training opportunity for women in this field. However, it remains unclear whether this is due to the general gender distribution within research infrastructures, gender differences in the utilization of professional development opportunities, or gender disparities in academic hierarchies. Nevertheless, these findings should be carefully considered in the future development of the RltrainPlus program.

Beyond content based concern based difficulties, specific structural concerns also emerge. A key point raised by participants is the importance of a well-structured program that allows them to integrate training into their professional responsibilities. Many participants are actively working while attending the courses, making it crucial to provide clear advance information, precise scheduling, and transparent communication regarding course content.

The data showed that professionals participated regardless of their geographical location. While a focus on Europe, and especially Italy, is evident, participation in the program was also open to individuals outside of this region. This was primarily due to the possibility of online participation and the scheduling of on-site events in blocks. Nevertheless, the RltrainPlus program is embedded within EU structures, regulations, and frameworks, which may create challenges for participants from outside of Europe. Research infrastructures and core facilities must be understood within this specific European context. While the program is accessible internationally, the alignment with European practices could make participation more difficult or less relevant for those working outside these systems.

Moreover, while the hybrid and online format of the program has improved accessibility, the organization of the courses could be further optimized for digital learning. Ensuring that workload and content align with the online format, providing high-quality learning materials, and structuring courses with appropriate breaks and pacing would enhance the learning experience. Additionally, while most courses were held online, the 'Coaching Development' course, which also offered an on-site component, was rated very positively in the survey. Interviews further emphasized that personal interaction—the exchange and connection with other participants—played a crucial role in the experience. To balance the benefits of flexible online learning with meaningful engagement, it would be valuable to integrate structured opportunities for networking and interpersonal exchange. This could include interactive elements in online courses and optional in-person meetings, allowing participants to build connections while maintaining the accessibility of the program.

To ensure the long-term success and relevance of the RltrainPlus program, it would be valuable to refine its structure by offering more broader course program as well as clearly defined course

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levels, improving communication about target audiences and prerequisites, and expanding outreach to underrepresented disciplines. At the same time, maintaining the program's accessibility while integrating opportunities for networking and peer exchange could further enhance its impact. By addressing these aspects, RltrainPlus can continue to provide valuable training while adapting to the existing needs in the field of research infrastructures and core facilities.

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